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**IMPLEMENTATION AND PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED ON THE
GUN CONTROL POLICIES BY PNP REGIONAL OFFICE
TOWARDS ITS ENHANCEMENT**

A Dissertation
Presented to the Faculty of the Graduate School
EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

**In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice**

**JULIUS BURIAS MELLIJOR
June 2022**

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APPROVAL SHEET

This Dissertation titled, “**THE IMPLEMENTATION AND PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED ON GUN CONTROL POLICIES BY POLICE REGIONAL OFFICE TOWARDS ITS ENCHANMENT**”, prepared and submitted by **Julius B Mellijor**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice** has been examined and recommended for acceptance for Oral Examination.

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DEDICATION

***T**his research is*

humbly and lovingly dedicated

To my family as they are my inspiration in life...

I also dedicated this to my friends, mentors, and core group of the

PNP Regional Civil

Security Unit 13 and Police Regional Office 13 (PRO13) for the

invaluable support of which I privilege of being part, above all, to

the Great Architect of the Universe, the ALMIGHTY Father.

Julius B Mellijor

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Above all, to the Most Holy Triune God, fountain of all wisdom and knowledge, whose constant blessings and enlightenment, grace of perseverance sustained all throughout the study.

MELLIJOR

JULIUS B

ABSTRACT

TITLE: IMPLEMENTATION AND PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED ON GUN CONTROL POLICIES BY POLICE REGIONAL OFFICE TOWARDS ITS ENCHANEMENT

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DEGREE: DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN CRIMINAL JUSTICE WITH SPECIALIZATION IN CRIMINOLOGY

DATE COMPLETED: June 2022

The study aimed to determine the implementation and problems encountered on the gun control polices by the PNP Regional Office towards Its Enhancement. There was a total of 200 respondents broken down to 50 police personnel assigned as LTOPF and Firearms processor and 150 Gun Owners to include Operators.

Specifically, this study sought to answer to the following questions.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following:

- 1.1. Operator/Gun Owners

- 1.1.1. educational attainment;
- 1.1.2. profession/occupation;
- 1.1.3. number of firearms in ownership;
- 1.1.4. number of years as holders of LTOPF; and
- 1.1.5. type of issued LTOPF?

1.2. PNP Personnel

- 1.2.1. length of service in the pnp; and
- 1.2.2. number of years serving as licensing officer?

2. What is the assessment of the PNP personnel and Operators/Gun Holders with LTOPF respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of the following:

- 2.1. enforcement; and
- 2.2. monitoring?

3. Is there a significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office?

4. What are the problems encountered by PNP personnel and Gun owners and Operators of LTOPF in Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office?

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5. Based on the results of the study, what enhancement plan can be crafted to support the effective implementation of the Gun Control Policies.

ABSTRACT

According to statistics, there is an increasing gun-related deaths, violence and trafficking of small arms are emergent consequents of failure towards gun regulation and irresponsible gun ownership worldwide. Thus, this study was conducted to examine the implementation of the Gun Control Policy in Caraga Region focusing on the aspect of enforcement and monitoring. Also, the study aimed to investigate the problems encountered in the implementation of the gun control policy in enforcement and monitoring with the gun owners/operators and PNP personnel as respondents. This study was conducted using the descriptive correlational research design.

The study revealed the following findings: Majority of the Gun Operator/Owner respondents are college level, employed to private institutions who owned 1 to 2 guns, license for 1-5 years, mostly under type-1 category. For the PNP Personnel respondents, most of them are purely Baccalaureate holders who served the organization for 6-10 years and have 5 to 10 years' experience as licensing officers. In terms of the enforcement and monitoring of the gun control policies, the respondents basically rated it as *Highly Implemented*. On the test of significance, there was a significant difference on the assessment of the respondents in gun control policy monitoring but showed to have no significant difference on the respondent's assessment in enforcement. Both Gun owners and PNP respondents considered the problems encountered in enforcement and monitoring as highly prevalent problems. On the test of significance, there was no significant difference in the assessment of the respondents for both enforcement and monitoring of Gun Control policies. On the test of significant

relationship, there was a significant relationship on the Gun control policies enforcement and monitoring with its problems encountered.

It can be concluded that the Gun Control policies were fairly implemented by the government despite the challenges like the problems encountered in its enforcement and monitoring. The problems encountered in enforcement and monitoring were highly prevalent thus it needs serious actions by the PNP organization. It can further be concluded that there is a correlation between the Gun control policies and its problems encountered. Thus, the PNP must conduct series of orientation and forum among the gun owners / operators to strengthen the implementation of the gun control policies, must adopt technology in a form of online app design to hasten the documentation and tracing of expired gun licenses, create more information campaign to prevent gun violence in the future maximizing various platforms, must create “hotline” call center as support mechanism in monitoring unregistered and lost firearms and create online gun licensing system.

Keywords: Gun control policies, gun licensing, Gun owners, operators

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INTRODUCTION

Today as the world changes, there are pressing concerns on the significance of illegitimate firearms unfortunately used on criminality and on the transnational organized crime. As society operates, unlawful firearms fuel conflicts, undermine security and hinder development in general reality. But a few preventive and security measures can be crafted to enhance regulatory mechanisms and policies in the fight against these serious threats.

Seemingly, Republic Act 10591 or the Comprehensive Firearms and Ammunition Regulation Act, an act providing for a comprehensive law on firearms and ammunition and providing penalties for violations thereof was crafted. RA 10591 stipulates that people seeking to carry a gun may apply for a Permit to Carry Firearm Outside Residence (PTCfor). Permits to Carry (PTCs) are granted on a May-Issue basis at the discretion of the issuing authority. A qualified person may apply for a PTC if he or she is under actual threat.

The law specifies professionals who are in imminent danger due to the nature of their profession, occupation, or business. These include lawyers or members of the Philippine Bar, certified

public accountants, accredited media practitioners, cashiers, bank tellers, priests, ministers, rabbis and imams, physicians, nurses, and engineers. Businessmen who, by nature of their business or undertaking, are exposed to the high risk of being targets of criminal elements are also allowed to apply for PTC. Section 10 of RA 10591 also specifies the firearms that may be registered. Only small firearms may be registered by licensed citizens or licensed juridical entities for ownership, possession, and concealed carrying.

In the country, there is increasing gun-related deaths, violence and trafficking of small arms are emergent consequents of failure towards gun regulation and irresponsible gun ownership worldwide. There were approximately 857 million civilian-held firearms in the world at the end of 2017 (Karp, June 2018). In the Philippines, gun-related violence is one of the challenging variables in the management of arms and ammunition for effective safekeeping operations. According to the World Health Organization's Inter-Country Comparison of Mortality for Selected Causes of Death, the Philippines annual deaths resulting from firearms have a total of 7,702 with an annual rate of 7.88 by 2014 from 7,296 in 2011 (WHO, 2021; Alpers, & Michael, 2021). Accordingly, in 2011, the Philippines has a total of 7,214 annual

firearm homicides and 38 annual firearm suicides. In 2014, there were 291 annual unintentional shooting deaths, and a total of 285 annual shooting deaths in which the cause remains undetermined (WHO, 2021; Alpers, & Michael, 2021).

Braga, et al. (2012) posited that comprehensive background check laws, by restricting access to firearms for individuals presumed to present a greater risk of misusing those firearms, licensing and permitting requirements are intended to reduce gun violence (Cook, 2020). Different designations for the types of conditions that disqualify an individual may generate differential impacts on such outcomes as homicide or mass shootings compared with suicides (Wamser-Nanney, 2021). Although compliance is likely to be imperfect, licensing and permitting laws may still reduce gun-related homicides or suicides by deterring prohibited possessors who do not already own firearms from attempting to acquire them. The magnitude of these effects will be influenced, in part, by the level of enforcement, the availability of firearms or ammunition through unregulated markets, and the likelihood that an individual who would be disqualified through the permitting process will seek to obtain a firearm through alternative markets (Rosenberg, 2021).

In the Philippines, the right to self-defense is a constitutional guarantee to gun ownership Halbrook (2020) and (Siegel, & Blocher, 2020). There are “pro” and “anti” positions as regards gun ownership. The topic is polarizing. In fact, in the Exploratory Note of Senate Bill 48 of Senator Lacson, “firearms smuggling is a dangerous but profitable criminal enterprise. It not only threatens public safety and national security but also endangers and oftentimes takes away the lives even of innocent persons. The possession of smuggled and loose firearms often emboldens the person in possession thereof to the commission of more serious offenses such as, but not limited to, murder, homicide, and rebellion, piracy, kidnapping, and armed robbery (Ahram, 2020).

According to Concepcion (2019), the estimated total number of guns (both licit and illicit) held by civilians in the Philippines is between 2,666,418 and 3,977,237 (Karp, 2018; Alpers, & Michael, 2021). In 2019, the number of registered guns in the Philippines is reported to be 1,940,237. Although the unregistered and unlawfully held guns cannot be counted, Concepcion estimated it to be between 726,181 and 2,037,000 in Karp's (2018) study on Estimating Global Civilian-Held Firearms Numbers. Karp (2018) also reported that the defense forces of the Philippines are

reported to have 454,700 firearms, and there were 139,043 firearms in and the Police in the Philippines.

Presently, illegal, unregistered, or unlicensed firearms have figured prominently in notorious high-profile drug heists, violent extremist activities, massacres, homicides, robberies, and similar crimes in the country. According to the Philippine National Police (PNP), as cited by Diega (2021), almost 99 percent of the guns used in these types of crimes are loose firearms. According to research done by International Alert-Philippines, Filipinos owned an estimated 3.9 million firearms in 2014. Some 2.1 million, or half of these, are illegal.

While the PNP Regional Civil Security Unit 13 (RCSU13) of the Police Regional Office 13 (PRO 13) has mobilized the Caraga-wide caravan to make it easier for gun owners to apply for a new license to own and possess firearms (LTOPF) and renewal of gun licenses, as such, it will also receive applications for LTOPF and the delinquent operator and gun owners to have their expired LTOPF's renewed and Firearm Registration, it has to intensify operations to prevent the proliferation of loose firearms (Caraga News Courier; April 4, 2017). Recently, a massive drive versus loose guns was ordered in the Bangsamoro Region in Muslim Mindanao, and in the Caraga region (Fernandez, & Lopez;

November 15, 2021). Accordingly, the drive against loose firearms ahead of the 2022 local and national elections was intensified to ensure the peaceful and orderly conduct of polls. These operations resulted in the arrest of 374 individuals with a total of 1,525 loose firearms that have already been confiscated in the region from January 2021 to November 2021, 830 of which were voluntarily surrendered to the different police stations and units in the area. Recognizing the multiple motives that gun control policies particularly in the CARAGA Region David, et al (2018), it is in this premise that this study will assess the implementation and explore on the pressing problems relevant to the implementation of the Philippine government laws and its IRR and addressing the problems encountered on the Gun Control Policies by PNP Regional Office Towards Its Enhancement on License To Own and Possess Firearm (LTOPF) and Firearms Registration in terms of regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by civilians; specific regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private security companies; regulations that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use; regional or international commitment(s) related to the regulation of civilian acquisition, possession or use of firearms undertaken by the Philippine

government; the types and characteristics of firearms to which civilians can lawfully have access; limitations on the number of firearms which civilians may own; categorization of firearms according to risk factors and how they are legally classified; the conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm; the system used to keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians; the conditions for the transfer of ownership of firearms between civilians; the measures in placed to regulate private entities engaged in selling firearms to civilians in the domestic market; the conditions required for private entities to fulfil in order to qualify for a license to sell firearms; the measures in placed to minimize the risk of firearms being misused by civilians; the simplicity of process flow of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearm Registration; and the firearms registration by cluster municipal, Cities and Province to bring the services near to the doorstep of the registered firearm holders and the would be who want to possess. It is a fact that many studies in the field of Criminology in Caraga Region were geared towards the improvement of the academe, Crimes and the PNP functions but minimal study interest towards the gun licensing, exploring its IRR's implementation flaws and pressing problems encountered in the Region.

This study will consider a retrospective presentation of previously written material: research literature and concepts relevant and significant to the research understudy that covers the Legislation and Regulation on Acquisition, Possession and Use of Firearms by Civilians; Legislation and Regulation on Acquisition, Possession and Use of Firearms by Private Security Companies; The Philippines Regional and International Commitments to the Regulation of Civilian Acquisition, Possession or use of Firearms; Types and Classification of Firearms that can be Lawfully Accessed by Civilians; Categories of Firearms According to Risk Factors; and the Impact of Domestic Regulation of Civilian Firearms on the Protection of the Right to Life and Security of Person.

In the Philippines, the ownership of firearms is regulated by the Firearms and Explosives Office of the Philippine National Police (Bustillo, & Mateo, 2020). The acquisition, possession and use of firearms by civilians is governed mainly by Republic Act No. 10591 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR), entitled: An Act Providing for a Comprehensive Law on Firearms and Ammunition and Providing Penalties for Violations Thereof” otherwise known as “Comprehensive Firearms and Ammunition Regulation Act” approved May 29, 2013 (De Castro, & Jimenez,

2013). Similarly, acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private companies are governed by RA 10591 and RA 5487 entitled An Act to Regulate the Organization and Operation of Private Detective, Watchmen or Security Guards Agencies June 21 1969 and the 2003 Revised Rules and Regulations Implementing (IRR) of RA 5487 as amended.

Considering its literature and related studies, accordingly, gun violence is a daily tragedy affecting the lives of individuals around the world. More than 500 people die every day because of violence committed with firearms (<https://www.amnesty.org/en>), hence the need of gun control. Gun control is the set of laws or policies that regulate the manufacture, sale, transfer, possession, modification, or use of firearms by civilians (Smith, & Spiegler, 2020). According to Kantack, & Paschall (2020), gun control and advocacies are usually escalated during or in the aftermath of a mass shooting. Hurka & Knill (2020) conducted a cross-national impact analysis of gun policies, as gun control was not only associated with lower rates of gun homicides and gun suicides but also impacted the overall homicide and suicide rates.

For those who believe that dangerous weapons cause war, the purpose of arms control is stability, or limiting especially dangerous offense-dominant weapons while bolstering deterrence

by allowing the procurement of defense-dominant weapons (Maurer, November 2018). Similarly, Smith & Spiegler (2020) determined the association of tougher gun control laws and greater access to mental health services affects the rate of gun deaths in American states. Accordingly, their work resulted in tougher gun control laws associated with a lower overall rate of gun deaths, and with a lower rate of non-suicide gun deaths, and reduction in the rate of gun-related suicides.

There are Types and Classification of Firearms that can be Lawfully Accessed by Civilians. Basically, a firearm is a barrelled ranged weapon that perpetrates damages and impairment on targets by launching one or more projectiles driven by rapidly expanding high-pressure gas produced by exothermic combustion (deflagration) of a chemical propellant, historically black powder, now smokeless powder (Cole, November 19, 2016). The subset of light firearms that only use kinetic projectiles and are compact enough to be operated to full capacity by a single infantryman is referred to as "small arms" (Weller, Guilmartin, Ezell, November 7, 2017).

Pursuant to Section 10 of Republic Act 10591, only small arms may be registered by licensed citizens or licensed juridical entities for ownership, possession, and concealed carry. The Comprehensive Firearms and Ammunition Regulation Act, officially recorded as Republic Act No. 10591, is a consolidation of Senate Bill No. 3397 and House Bill No. 5484. It was enacted

and passed by the Senate of the Philippines and the House of Representatives of the Philippines on February 4, 2013, and February 5, 2013, respectively. It was signed into law by President Benigno Aquino III on May 29, 2013. The basis of Republic Act No. 10591 was to efficiently improve and provide stiffer penalties on illegal firearm acquisition and possession (De Castro, & Jimenez, 2013).

Further, there are limitations on the number of firearms that civilians may possess Pursuant to Section 9.1 of the IRR of RA 10591. Accordingly, a qualified individual based on the findings and recommendations of the Firearms and Explosive Office-Philippine National Police. The Firearms and Explosive Office-Philippine National Police administer, enforce, and implement the firearms and explosives laws, rules, and regulations in the Philippines (Pascua, 2018). Civilians with issued licenses to Own and Possess are entered into the Firearms Information Management System (FIMS), a computerized system that establishes a database of the licensee and the registered firearms information and generates reports which include the printing of license and certificate of registration and disposition.

The FEO Classification Board (FCB) or the FEO classification body has the regulatory role to classify firearms, ammunition, explosives, explosives ingredients and other

regulated items prior to sale, distribution and/or exhibition to ensure that such items conform to existing laws and regulations (Philippines, 2013). Accordingly, a civilian maybe issued of any the licenses hereunder : Type 1 license – this license allows a citizen to own and possess a maximum of two (2) registered firearms; Type 2 license – this license allows a citizen to own and possess a maximum of five (5) registered firearms; Type 3 license – this license allows a citizen to own and possess a maximum ten (10) registered firearms; Type 4 license – this license allows a citizen to own and possess a maximum of fifteen (15) registered firearms; and Type 5 license - this license allows a citizen, who is certified gun collector, to own and possess more than fifteen (15) registered firearms.

Categories of Firearms According to Risk Factors.

While most people believe that gun ownership is a significant tool of self-preservation, opposition to owning firearms consider owning guns as a menace to public safety (Pierre, 2019). Many of the risk factors of having guns were the increasing deaths and suicides related to guns.

In the Philippines, firearms were legally classified by the FEO Classification Board (FCB), the FEO classification body with a regulatory role to classify firearms, ammunition, explosives,

explosives ingredients and other regulated items prior to sale, distribution and/or exhibition to ensure that such items conform to existing laws and regulations. Further, firearms are categorized according to risk factors. Under RA 10591 and its IRR firearms are categorized into two (2) category Small Arms and Light Weapons defined as follows:

Small Arms are firearms intended to be primarily designed for individual use or that which is generally considered to mean a weapon intended to be fired from the hand or shoulder, which are not capable of fully automatic bursts of discharge, such as: Handgun, Rifle, and Shotgun. On the other hand, Light Weapons are: Class-A Light weapons which refer to self-loading pistols, rifles, carbines, submachine guns, assault rifles and light machine guns not exceeding caliber 7.62MM which have fully automatic mode; and Class-B Light weapons which refer to weapons designed for use by two (2) or more persons serving as a crew, or rifles and machine guns exceeding caliber 7.62MM such as heavy machine guns, handheld under barrel and mounted grenade launchers, portable anti-aircraft guns, portable anti-tank missile and rocket systems, portable launchers of anti-aircraft missile systems, and mortars of a caliber of less than 100MM.

On the other hand, Small Arms are classified as Handgun, Rifle, and Shotgun. Handgun is a firearm intended to be fired from the hand, which includes Pistol - is a hand-operated firearm having a chamber integral with or permanently aligned with the bore which may be self-loading; and Revolver - is a hand-operated firearm with a revolving cylinder containing chambers for individual cartridges.

While, Rifle is a shoulder firearm or designed to be fired from the shoulder that can discharge a bullet through a rifled barrel by different actions of loading, which may be classified as lever, bolt, or self-loading; and Shotgun is a firearm designed, made and intended to fire a number of ball shots or a single projectile through a smooth bore by the action or energy from burning gunpowder.

The United Nations General Assembly defined small arms as any man-portable lethal weapon that expels or launches, is designed to expel or launch, or maybe readily converted to expel or launch a shot, bullet, or projectile by the action of an explosive, excluding antique small arms and light weapons or their replicas (United Nations General Assembly, 25 February 2013). On the other hand, light weapons" are weapons designed for use by two or three people serving as a crew, although some may be carried and used by a single person (NATO, 15 February 2021).

The Philippines Regional and International Commitments to the Regulation of Civilian Acquisition, Possession, or use of Firearms.

According to Nystuen, & Egeland (2019), Philippines is a signatory to the Arms Trade Treaty and manifest its commitment to the UN Programme of Action (UN PoA) Bromund, (2021) and Acheson & Butler (2019) to Prevent, Combat and Eradicate the Illicit Trade in SALW in all its Aspects, the International Tracing Instruments and Protocol Against the Illicit Manufacturing of and Trafficking in Firearms, their Parts and Components and Ammunition where some provisions of said instruments tackle civilian acquisition, possession or use of firearms such as in the aspect of record keeping and tracing.

The Arms Trade Treaty (ATT) is an international treaty that came into force on December 24, 2014, that regulates the international trade in conventional arms and seeks to prevent and eradicate illicit trade and diversion of conventional arms by establishing international standards governing arms transfers (Nave, 2019). According to United Nations Regional Centre for Peace and Disarmament, the UN Program of Action to Prevent, Combat and Eradicate the Illicit Trade in Small Arms and Light Weapons (PoA) is a globally agreed framework for activities to counter the illicit trade in small arms and light weapons and control the negative consequences of Small Arms and Light Weapons (Нагорний, 2019). Accordingly, the proliferation of small arms and

light weapons in Asia and the Pacific has been the result of several factors. Parts of Asia remain affected by armed conflict, from inter-state war and sectarian conflict to protracted or guerrilla warfare.

Impact of Domestic and International Regulation of Civilian and Private Companies Firearms on the Protection of the Right to Life and Security of Person.

Similarly, domestic regulation of firearms on the protection of the right to life and security of person is ensuring that persons who own or has the desire to own, possess or carry firearms outside residence are those who are qualified only within the limits set by laws especially private security agencies (Smith, 2020). Particularly, this regulatory measure recognizes human rights protection Galavís (2020) as it ensures that holders are responsible gun owners and have sufficient knowledge and skills in the proper handling of firearms Donnelly & Whelan (2020) as set forth under existing laws, rules, and regulations (Solovyeva and Hynek, 2021). Swanson, Barry, & Swartz (2020) opined regulating firearm accessibility has also been seen to curb intentional firearm-related injury such as suicide particularly as these approaches intersect with mental health policy. As a global public safety goal, national and international instruments should

collide together to accelerate a world with free gun-related incidents (Blocher, Buell, Charles, & Miller, 2020).

The Philippines is a signatory to the Arms Trade Treaty, and manifest its commitment to the UN Program of Action (UN PoA) Bromund (2021) to Prevent, Combat and Eradicate the Illicit Trade in SALW in all its Aspects, the International Tracing Instruments and Protocol Against the Illicit Manufacturing of and Trafficking in Firearms, their Parts and Components and Ammunition where some provisions of said instruments tackle civilian acquisition, possession or use of firearms such as in the aspect of record keeping and tracing.

The acquisition, possession, and use of firearms by civilians is governed mainly by Republic Act No. 10591 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR), entitled: An Act Providing for a Comprehensive Law on Firearms and Ammunition and Providing Penalties for Violations Thereof” otherwise known as “Comprehensive Firearms and Ammunition Regulation Act” approved May 29, 2013. Similarly, the regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private companies are governed by RA 10591 and RA 5487 entitled An Act to Regulate the Organization and Operation of Private Detective, Watchmen or Security Guards Agencies June 21, 1969, and the

2003 Revised Rules and Regulations Implementing (IRR) of RA 5487 as amended.

Further, the country has relevant legislation, regulations, administrative procedures, policies, or any other measures that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use as the mandate of the Philippine National Police Firearms and Explosives Office. The Philippine National Police Firearms and Explosives Office is the responsible office for the issuances, management and revocation of License To Own and Possess Firearm (LTOPF), and Firearms Application and Renewal including the Juridical Entity Application for Regular License, License to Manufacture in Firearm and its Major Parts Small Arm Spare Parts and Accessories, License to Manufacture in Ammunition and/or Ammunition Reloading Components, License to Manufacture in Ammunition in Minor Parts and Accessories, License to Manufacture in Minor Parts and Accessories, License to Manufacture in Airguns/Airsoft, License to Manufacture in Bullet Proof Vest/Vestment, and License to Manufacture in Sporting Rifle/Scope.

As to its **background of the study**, aimed to assess the implementation of the Philippine government laws and policies particularly to the PNP Regional Office on License to Own and

Possess Firearm (LTOPF) and Firearms Registration in the CARAGA Region with the intent of proposing Towards Its Enhancement of Gun Control Policies. The study will be conducted in the PNP Firearms Licensing Offices in CARAGA Region. The researcher forwarded the idea that the results of this study will provide solutions on Problems Encountered on the Gun Control Policies of the existing License to Own and Possess Firearms (LTOPF) and Firearms Registration procedures and processes; thus, these can be used to make insights or recommendations for future enhancement programs. The recommendation implies Towards Its Enhancement of Gun Ownership Policies will also help the person perform well in the workplace and help gun owners become more aware and responsible.

The **Theoretical Framework** of this study is anchored on RA NO. 10591 or the *Act Providing for a Comprehensive Law on Firearms and Ammunition and Providing Penalties for Violations Thereof*. It is the policy of the State to maintain peace and order and protect the people against violence. The State also recognizes the right of its qualified citizens to self-defense through, when it is the reasonable means to repel the unlawful aggression under the circumstances, the use of firearms. Towards this end, the State shall provide for a comprehensive law regulating the ownership,

possession, carrying, manufacture, dealing in and importation of firearms, ammunition, or parts thereof, in order to provide legal support to law enforcement agencies in their campaign against crime, stop the proliferation of illegal firearms or weapons and the illegal manufacture of firearms or weapons, ammunition and parts thereof.

In this study, the **conceptual framework** to be used by the research is presented in Figure1, the research paradigm. The Independent Variables covered the profile of the operator/gun owner-respondents in terms of educational attainment, profession/occupation, number of firearms in ownership, number of years as holders of LTOPF, and type of issued LTOPF as well as PNP Personnel's profile such as length of service in the PNP and number of years serving as licensing officer while the Dependent Variables dealt with the assessments of the PNP personnel and Operators/Gun Holders with LTOPF respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of enforcement and monitoring as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

The study aimed to determine the implementation and problems encountered on the gun control policies by the PNP Regional Office towards Its Enhancement. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions in the **statement of the problem:**

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Operator/Gun Owners
 - 1.1.1. educational attainment;
 - 1.1.2. profession/occupation;
 - 1.1.3. number of firearms in ownership;
 - 1.1.4. number of years as holders of LTOPF; and
 - 1.1.5. type of issued LTOPF?

1.2. PNP Personnel

1.2.1. length of service in the pnp; and

1.2.2. number of years serving as licensing officer?

2. What is the assessment of the PNP personnel and Operators/Gun Holders with LTOPF respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of the following:

2.1. enforcement; and

2.2. monitoring?

3. Is there a significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office?

4. What are the problems encountered by PNP personnel and Gun owners and Operators of LTOPF in Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office?

5. Based on the results of the study, what enhancement plan can be crafted to support the effective implementation of the Gun Control Policies.

Considering the foregoing research questions, the following **research hypothesis** is presented herewith:

1. There is no significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office?

As to the **significance of the study**, the findings and the suggested recommendations would enhance the implementation of the Gun Control Policies by PNP Regional Office Towards Its Enhancement shall benefit the following:

To the Hierarchy of the Philippine National Police (PNP).

The data and findings of this study can be used as baseline data to formulate future enhancement Implementation and address the Problems Encountered on the Gun Control Policies efficiently and excellently on Firearms Registration and processing of License to Own and Possess Firearms (LTOPF) procedures.

To the Personnel of PNP Firearms Licensing Office (LTOPF). The results and findings of this study will provide an initial actual assessment or evaluation of the effectiveness of the existing License to Own and Possess Firearms (LTOPF) procedures and processes, thus, these can be used to make insights or suggested recommendations for future enhancement

programs. The recommended Enhanced Gun Ownership Program will also help the person perform well in the workplace operator and help gun owners become more aware and responsible.

To the Operators and Gun owners. The results of the study will serve as a guide and basis for more awareness of the rules and regulations, relevant mandates, policies, by the Operators and Gun owners which will implemented by the PNP Regional Office.

To The Researcher. The study will allow the researcher to explore the many facets of the Philippine government laws and policies on License to Own and Possess Firearm (LTOPF) and Firearms Registration relevant legislation, regulations, administrative procedures, policies, or any other measures, such that, examine the stakeholders' perceptions of the stakeholders, toward its implementation of the same mandates and measures. Further, the study allowed the researcher to investigate other areas of policing in criminological phenomenon to keep a peaceful, orderly, and free society. Moreover, this contribution of the researcher to the existing knowledge will help the proponent professionally and academically in doing scholarly works.

To The Future Researchers. This study will help future researchers who would like to focus on firearms licensing and ownership research domain. The findings and research

instruments can be used in the same perceptive study in a larger population and stakeholders. Further, the suggested recommended output of the study can be assessed towards its enhancement, design, and further improvement may be recommended to make it responsive and adaptive to the demands of dynamic gun ownership policy and environment.

The **scope and delimitation of the study** only determined the Implementation and problems encountered in the Gun Control Policies by the PNP Regional Office.

The study also determined the significant difference in the perceived implementation on the Philippine government laws and policies on License To Own and Possess Firearm (LTOPF) relevant legislation, regulations, administrative procedures, policies or any other measures such as the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by civilians is governed mainly by Republic Act No. 10591 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations; the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private companies are governed by RA 10591 and RA 5487 entitled An Act To Regulate The Organization And Operation Of Private Detective, Watchmen Or Security Guards Agencies; only small arms may be registered by licensed citizens or licensed juridical entities for ownership, possession and concealed carry; there are limits on the

number of firearms that civilians may possess; civilians are required to have a License to Own and Posses Firearm (LTOPF) for him/her to be authorized to acquire, own/possess or use a firearm; firearms must always be concealed; firearm must be secured inside a vehicle or a motor cycle compartment; and firearm shall not be brought inside places of worship, public drinking and amusement places and all other commercial or public establishment as assessed by the two groups of respondents.

Similarly, the study also determined the significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office such as the regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by civilians; specific regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private security companies; regulations that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use; regional or international commitment(s) related to the regulation of civilian acquisition, possession or use of firearms undertaken by the Philippine government; the types and characteristics of firearms to which civilians can lawfully have access; limitations on the number of firearms which civilians may own; categorization of

firearms according to risk factors and how they are legally classified; the conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm; the system used to keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians; the conditions for the transfer of ownership of firearms between civilians; the measures in placed to regulate private entities engaged in selling firearms to civilians in the domestic market; the conditions required for private entities to fulfil in order to qualify for a license to sell firearms; and the measures in placed to minimize the risk of firearms being misused by civilians as assessed by the two groups of respondents.

The perceived Implementation and Problems Encountered on the Gun Control Policies by PNP Regional Office Towards Its Enhancement on License To Own and Possess Firearm (LTOPF) and Firearms Registration such as the regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by civilians; specific regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private security companies; regulations that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use; regional or international commitment(s) related to the regulation of civilian acquisition, possession or use of firearms undertaken by the Philippine government; the types and

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characteristics of firearms to which civilians can lawfully have access; limitations on the number of firearms which civilians may own; categorization of firearms according to risk factors and how they are legally classified; the conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm; the system used to keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians; the conditions for the transfer of ownership of firearms between civilians; the measures in placed to regulate private entities engaged in selling firearms to civilians in the domestic market; the conditions required for private entities to fulfil in order to qualify for a license to sell firearms; and the measures in placed to minimize the risk of firearms being misused by civilians; the simplicity of process flow of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearm Registration; and the firearms registration by cluster municipal, Cities and Province to bring the services near to the doorstep of the registered firearm holders would be who want to possess as assessed by the gun owners and operators will be correlated with the following profile variates: age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, source of income, nature of work/ business, position, monthly gross income, number of guns in possession/ownership, number of years since a license to own and possessed was obtained, and

number of seminars on gun safety and responsible gun ownership attended.

Furthermore, the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office such as the regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by civilians; specific regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private security companies; regulations that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use; regional or international commitment(s) related to the regulation of civilian acquisition, possession or use of firearms undertaken by the Philippine government; the types and characteristics of firearms to which civilians can lawfully have access; limitations on the number of firearms which civilians may own; categorization of firearms according to risk factors and how they are legally classified; the conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm; the system used to keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians; the conditions for the transfer of ownership of firearms between civilians; the measures in placed to regulate private entities engaged in selling firearms to civilians in the

domestic market; the conditions required for private entities to fulfill in order to qualify for a license to sell firearms; and the measures in placed to minimize the risk of firearms being misused by civilians; the simplicity of process flow of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearm Registration; and the firearms registration by cluster municipal, Cities and Province to bring the services near to the doorstep of the registered firearm holders who want to possess as assessed by the PNP Firearms Licensing Office- CARAGA Region employees will be correlated with the following profile variates: age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, position/rank, monthly gross income, number of guns in possession/ownership, number of seminars on gun safety and responsible gun ownership attended, number of years since a license to own and possessed was obtained, type of issued license, and number of years of working in the PNP Firearms Licensing Office.

The study covered 200 respondents. The 1st group of respondents was composed of 150-gun owners/operators, while the 2nd group of respondents was composed of 50 Personnel of PNP Firearms Licensing Offices in CARAGA Region.

This study was conducted during the School Year 2021 – 2022. Data gathering will commence in June 2022.

To help the readers to have a better understanding about this study, the following terms/variables are **operationally defined**: the following terms are herein defined conceptually and operationally.

FEO Classification Board (FCB). It refers to the FEO classification body with a regulatory role to classify firearms, ammunition, explosives, explosives ingredients and other regulated items prior to sale, distribution and/or exhibition to ensure that such items conform to existing laws and regulations.

FEO License Revocation and Restoration Board (FLRRB). It refers to the FEO board with a regulatory function to study, review, validate and recommend the correction, deletion, revocation, cancellation, suspension or restoration of all issued licenses, registrations and permits relative to firearms and explosives through a Resolution.

Firearm. It refers to a barreled ranged weapon that perpetrates damages and impairment on targets by launching one or more projectiles driven by rapidly expanding high-pressure gas produced by exothermic combustion (deflagration) a chemical propellant, historically black powder, now smokeless powder.

Firearms and Explosive Office- Philippine National Police. It refers to the Firearms and Explosives Office of the

Philippine National Police. The FEO administers, enforces and implements the firearms and explosives laws, rules and regulations in the Philippines.

Firearms Information Management System (FIMS). It refers to a computerized system that establishes a database of the licensee and the registered firearms information and generates reports which include the printing of license and certificate of registration and disposition.

Gun control policies. It refers to the set of laws or policies that regulate the manufacture, sale, transfer, possession, modification, or use of firearms by civilians.

Gun licensee. It refers to the act of owning a gun, either legal or illegal.

Handgun. It refers to a firearm intended to be fired from the hand, which includes:

Pistol. It refers to a hand-operated firearm having a chamber integral with or permanently aligned with the bore which may be self-loading.

Revolver. It refers to a hand-operated firearm with a revolving cylinder containing chambers for individual cartridges.

Rifle. It refers to a shoulder firearm or designed to be fired from the shoulder that can discharge a bullet through a rifled barrel

by different actions of loading, which may be classified as lever, bolt, or self-loading.

Shotgun. It refers to a firearm designed, made and intended to fire a number of ball shots or a single projectile through a smooth bore by the action or energy from burning gunpowder.

Small Arms. It refers to firearms intended to be primarily designed for individual use or that which is generally considered to mean a weapon intended to be fired from the hand or shoulder, which are not capable of fully automatic bursts of discharge.

METHODOLOGY

This part presents the locale of the study; research design; population, sample, and sampling techniques; data gathering procedure; research instrument; statistical treatment of data; and ethical considerations.

The *locale of the study* was conducted in the PNP Firearms Licensing Offices in CARAGA Region, a counterpart of Philippine National Police Firearms and Explosives Office. The Philippine National Police Firearms and Explosives Office is the responsible office for the License To Own and Possess Firearm (LTOPF), and Firearms Application and Renewal including the Juridical Entity Application for Regular License, License to Manufacture in Firearm

and its Major Parts Small Arm Spare Parts and Accessories, License to Manufacture in Ammunition and/or Ammunition Reloading Components, License to Manufacture in Ammunition in Minor Parts and Accessories, License to Manufacture in Minor Parts and Accessories, License to Manufacture in Airguns/Airsoft, License to Manufacture in Bullet Proof Vest/Vestment, and License to Manufacture in Sporting Riflescope.

As to the **research design**, the study was conducted using the descriptive correlational research design (Anestis, & Houtsma, 2018). Foster, et al., (2020) posit that descriptive research provides a snapshot of the current state, while correlational research design is used to discover relationships among variables. Bloomfield and Fisher (2019) used descriptive correlational research design to describe the variables and to determine whether two or more variables are related. McAuley (2019) utilized the same research design to examine whether there were relationships between servant-leader behavior and organizational trust 12 performing-arts non-profit boards.

In particular, the descriptive phase was used in determining the profile of the licensed gun owner/operator respondents, and the personnel of PNP Firearms Licensing Office respondents as to educational attainment, profession/occupation, number of firearms

in ownership, number of years as holders of LTOPF, and type of issued LTOPF as well as length of service in the PNP and number of years serving as licensing officer, respectively. Using Weighted Mean, the assessments of the PNP personnel and Operators/Gun Holders with LTOPF respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of enforcement and monitoring were also determined. Finally, to test the significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office, ANOVA was used.

The ***population, sample and sampling techniques***, of this study had two (2) types of research respondents and applied Purposive Sampling technique. The respondents were chosen based on their location and availability for the gun owners who have good standing according to the PNP records. The first group of respondents were composed of gun owners and gun operators in the CARAGA Region, while the second group of respondents comprised the personnel of PNP Firearms Licensing Offices in CARAGA Region. Particularly, one hundred fifty (150) gun owners and gun operators in the CARAGA Region will be sampled, and (fifty) 50 personnel of PNP Firearms Licensing

Offices in the CARAGA Region will be sampled in the study as presented in Table 1. Based on statistics, there are a total of 8,409 Gun owners in Caraga Region, a total of 78 Gun operators. Also, a total of 97 PNP officers are assigned in the licensing department for the region. From this big significant population, the researcher will select operators and gun owners who will be applying the application of his license, permit, whether it is new applicant or renewal by possessing and engaging trades on firearms its either through walk-in and or availing of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearm Registration caravan regulated by the PNP Regional Office. Further, the gathering of data/s will be using purposive sampling technique with the prepared survey questionnaires by the research with thorough identifying the firearm records of the individual firearm holders and operators as a target respondent of the research studies as shown the tabulated table below, to wit:

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents (Actual Figures re PRO Caraga)

Respondents	Population	Target Size
Gun Owners	8,409	100
Gun Operators	78	50
PNP Personnel	97	50

The respondents were selected using the Purposive Sampling technique also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling is a sampling technique in which researcher relies on his or her own judgment when choosing members of respondents to participate the survey study. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique used with both qualitative and quantitative research techniques. Research students mostly use it as an effective tool while studying a specific cultural domain with proficient experts. Here the researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing the population members to participate in their surveys. That is why this sampling technique is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The researcher will just target 150-gun owners including gun operators and 50 PNP personnel assigned at the PNP licensing office of Caraga Region.

As to the ***data gathering procedure***, once the proposal is approved by the dissertation committee, request letters were addressed to the Officer-in-Charge (OICs) in different offices of the PNP Firearms Licensing Office in the CARAGA Region to conduct the study will be prepared with endorsement from the proponent's research adviser. These letters were personally delivered to the OICs with the proper presentation of the purposes

of the survey. Upon approval the researcher printed the validated research questionnaires and generated an online survey questionnaire using Google Form, as such, the researcher sought assistance from other PNP personnel in distributing and answering the questionnaire.

The study used both online and offline modalities during the administration of survey questionnaires. Hence, printed copies of the questionnaires were made available and administered to the target respondents. Furthermore, the questionnaires were made available using Google Forms. Google Forms is survey administration software included as part of the free, web-based Google Docs Editors suite offered by Google (Kalnow, Lloyd, Casey, & Little, 2019). The online survey link that was generated by the researcher was sent to the social media account or personal email of the target respondents.

Data gathered via Google Forms were downloaded from the researcher's Google Drive to the researcher's local computer/laptop repository. Data gathered through the offline modality were tabulated and merged with the data gathered online. Once the data are combined, data were analyzed using the specified statistical tools utilizing the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). SPSS Statistics is a software package

used for interactive, or batched, statistical analysis (George, & Mallery, 2019).

As to the *research instrument* used, the researcher-made survey questionnaire was used as the main data gathering instrument (Patterson, & Brandner, 2018). There were two (2) sets of questionnaires that were designed. Set A was intended to gather data from the gun owners and operators as the first group of respondents, while Set B was intended to gather data from the personnel of the PNP Firearms Licensing Office as the second group of respondents.

The set of questionnaires were subjected to content validation by at least five (5) researchers or subject matter experts using the measures of internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha (Emerson, 2019). The Cronbach alpha, the most common test score reliability coefficient for single administration was used to determine if the instrument is reliable and valid (Bitan, et al., 2020).

The survey questionnaire was designed to gather the needed data directly from the gun owners and operators and the PNP personnel in Caraga Region who are directly involved in the firearms licensing office of the same region. The detailed contents of the survey questionnaires are presented in the attached as one

of the annexes. In the computation of the data gathered, it was subjected to the four-point Likert Scale, as follows: 4-Strongly Agree (SA)/Much Aware (MA)/Very Effective (VE)/Very Serious (VS); 3-Agree (A)/Aware(A)/Serious (S); 2-Disagree (DA)/Less Effective (LE)/Less Serious (LS); 1-Strongly Disagree (SD)/Not Effective (NE)/Not Serious (NS).

For its Scoring Procedure, the illustrated Likert scale below are as follows:

Table 2

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.70 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Implementation is Very Effective /very frequent
3	2.80 – 3.69	Agree	Implementation is Effective / frequent
2	1.90 – 2.79	Disagree	Implementation is Fair/ less existing
1	1.00 – 1.89	Strongly Disagree	Implementation is Poor/ not existing

Since the study is using a descriptive correlational research design, descriptive and inferential statistical tools were used to **statistically treat the data** to be collected to answer for the research problems in the study.

To answer Problems Number 1, frequency and percentage distribution will be used to describe the profile of the respondents. Frequency distribution is a list, table or graph that displays the frequency of various outcomes in a sample (Vorobev, 2019). Percentage Distribution is a frequency distribution in which the individual class frequencies are expressed as a percentage of the total frequency equated to 100 (McFarland, 2019).

To answer Problems Number 2 and 4, Weighted Mean and Rank were utilized to determine and interpret the respondents' assessments of the PNP personnel and Operators/Gun Holders with LTOPF respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office as well as the problems encountered by PNP personnel and Gun owners and Operators of LTOPF in Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office. Weighted average is a calculation that considers the varying degrees of importance of the numbers in a data set (Gong, & Goksel, 2019).

To answer Problems Number 3, ANOVA was used to know the significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office.

Following *ethical considerations* and in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, data gathered were kept with the utmost confidentiality. Informed consent was obtained from the respondents before they could proceed with answering the survey. The participants were oriented so that they can freely withdraw anytime when they wish not to continue to participate anymore because of some constraints.

RESULTS:

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter primarily deals with the data of the study which were collected and generated during the period of investigation. This study was conducted to know the assessment of the PNP personnel and Operators/Gun Holders with LTOPF respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office with the end view of providing inputs for enrichment program.

Statement of the Problem #1: What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following:

Operator/Gun Owners: **educational attainment; profession/occupation; number of firearms in ownership; number of years as holders of LTOPF; and Type of Issued LTOPF?**

PNP Personnel: **Educational attainment; length of service in the PNP number of years serving as Licensing Officer?**

Table 1

Frequency and percentage distribution of the Gun Owner-respondents in terms of their profile

Category	Frequency	Percent
Educational attainment		
High school graduate and below	29	19.0
College undergraduate	85	57.0

College graduate	32	21.0
Postgraduate	4	3.0
Total	150	100.0
Profession/Occupation		
Public employment	46	31.0
Private employment	55	37.0
Self-employed	42	28.0
Overseas employment	7	5.0
Total	150	100.0
Number of firearms in possession/ownership		
1-2	94	63.0
3-5	31	21.0
6-10	19	13.0
11-15	6	4.0
Total	150	100.0
Number of years as holder of LTOPF		
5 years and below	87	58.0
6-10 years	39	26.0
11-15 years	19	13.0
Above 15 years	5	3.0
Total	150	100.0
Type of Issued License to Own and Possess Firearms		
Type 1	87	58.0
Type 2	22	15.0
Type 3	24	16.0
Type 4	14	9.0
Type 5	3	2.0
Total	150	100.0

Table-1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the Gun Owners- respondents in terms of their profile.

In terms of Educational Attainment, majority (f=85, 57.0 percent) of the surveyed respondents are college undergraduate followed by college graduate (f=32, 21.0 percent), High School graduate and

below (f=29, 19.0 percent) and four (4) Postgraduate or 3.0 percent of the total sample. It can be inferred that since most of the surveyed respondents have reached college level, the assumption is, they are literate and will have a better judgement and assessment of Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office.

In terms of Profession/Occupation, most (f=55, 37.0 percent) of the respondents are working privately, followed by forty-six (46) respondents who are working in public office or in the government or 31.0 percent of the total sample. In addition, there are self-employed respondents which comprises 28.0 percent of the total sample or forty-two (42) in number, and finally a handful (f=7, 5.0 percent) of respondents who are working abroad or part of the Overseas Filipino Workers (OFW) workforce.

Regarding the number of firearms in possession/ownership, the majority (f=94, 63.0 percent) of the respondents have 1-2 guns in their possession, followed by 3-5 (f=31, 21.0 percent), 6-10 (f=19, 13.0), and 11-15 (f=6, 4.0 percent).

In terms of the number of years as holder of LTOPF, most (f=87, 58.0 percent) of the gun owner- respondents have been holders for less than 5 years. Further, there are thirty-nine respondents or 26.0

percent of the total sample who are holders for 6-10 years, followed by 11-15 years (f=19, 13.0 percent), and 15 years and above (f=5, 3.0 percent).

And lastly, in terms of type of issued license to own and possess firearms, Type 1 has the greatest number of possessors (f=87, 58.0 percent), followed by Type 3 (f=24, 16.0 percent), Type 2 (f=22, 15.0 percent), Type 4 (f=14, 9.0 percent), and lastly the Type 5 (f=3, 2.0 percent).

Anyone can be affected by firearm violence but in certain situations gun violence disproportionately impacts communities of color, women, and other marginalized groups in society. Sometimes, the mere presence of firearms can make people feel threatened and fearful for their lives with severe and long-term psychological effects on individuals and whole communities. (amnesty.org,2020).

Table 2

Frequency and percentage distribution of the PNP Personnel-respondents in terms of their profile

Category	Frequency	Percent
Length of Service		
5 Years and below	16	32.0
6-10 Years	23	46.0
11-15 Years	6	12.0
Above 15 Years	5	10.0
Total	50	100.0
Number of years a Licensing Officer		
5 Years and below	16	32.0

6-10 Years	23	46.0
11-15 Years	6	12.0
Above 15 Years	5	10.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the PNP Personnel- respondents in terms of their profile.

In terms of length of service, the majority (f=23, 46.0 percent) of the respondents have been in service for 6-10 years, followed by 5 years and below (f=16, 32.0 percent), 11-15 years (f=6, 12.0 percent), and 15 years and above (f=5, 10.0 percent).

And for the number of years as a Licensing Officer, most (f=23, 46.0 percent) of the respondents have been in the position for 6-10 years and there are sixteen (16) respondents or 32.0 percent based on total sample to have below 5 years of tenure. Further, there are few (f=6, 12.0 percent) who hold the position for 11-15 years and five (5) (10.0 percent) officers with 15 years and above tenure.

Law enforcement is the next element of the criminal justice response. Its purpose is to prevent, detect and investigate firearms offences. Improving the investigative and detective capabilities of the criminal justice system, combined with efforts to improve cooperation, contributes to an increased understanding of the role

of firearms, thus helping to deter, detect, punish and prevent firearm offences (unodc.org,2021).

Statement of the Problem #2: What is the assessment of the PNP personnel and Operators/Gun Holders with LTOPF respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of enforcement and monitoring.

Table 3

Assessment of the Respondents on Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Enforcement

Indicators	Gun Operators/Owners		PNP Personnel	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
The acquisition, possession, and use of firearms by civilians is governed mainly by Republic Act No. 10591 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations.	3.77	0.59	3.80	0.49
The acquisition, possession, and use of firearms by private companies are governed by RA 10591 and RA 5487 entitled An Act to Regulate the Organization and Operation of Private Detective, Watchmen or Security Guards Agencies.	3.72	0.52	3.78	0.54
Only small arms may be registered by licensed citizens or licensed juridical entities for ownership, possession, and concealed carry.	3.66	0.47	3.80	0.49
There are limits on the number of firearms that civilians may possess.	3.93	0.36	3.85	0.37

Civilians are required to have a License to Own and Posses Firearm (LTOPF) for him/her to be authorized to acquire, own/possess, or use a firearm.	3.96	0.28	3.78	0.54
Firearms must always be concealed.	3.95	0.21	3.83	0.37
Firearm must be secured inside a vehicle or a motorcycle compartment.	3.95	0.21	3.76	0.59
Firearm shall not be brought inside places of worship, public drinking, and amusement places and all other commercial or public establishment.	3.92	0.27	3.82	0.43
Overall Mean and SD	3.86	0.36	3.80	0.48
Description	Highly Implemented		Highly Implemented	

Legend:

- 3.51-4.00 Highly Implemented and observed /Highly Prevailing problem
- 2.51-3.50 Implemented and Observed/ Prevailing problem
- 1.51-2.50 Less Implemented and observed/ Less Prevailing Problem
- 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented/ Not Prevailing problem

Table 3 presents the assessment of the respondents on Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Enforcement with an overall mean of 3.86 and 3.80 for gun owners/operators and PNP Personnel, respectively, which are both interpreted as ‘Highly Implemented.’

Basically, the gun owner-respondents believed that indicator: Civilians are required to have a License to Own and Posses Firearm (LTOPF) for him/her to be authorized to acquire, own/possess or

use a firearm was highly implemented with the highest mean value of 3.96 while the PNP personnel assessed that indicator: There are limits on the number of firearms that civilians may possess was highly implemented with the mean value of 3.85. From the result, it is very appropriate that LTOPF must strictly be followed with limit or control on the number of firearms to prevent gun violence in the future.

However, indicator: Only small arms may be registered by licensed citizens or licensed juridical entities for ownership, possession, and concealed carry; and Firearm must be secured inside a vehicle, or a motorcycle compartment got the lowest mean value of 3.66 and 3.76 respectively. It is imperative that all types of guns be regulated, and the gun owners must be extra cautious in securing their guns in the vehicle.

Gun control is one of the most controversial and emotional issues in many countries, with the debate often centering on whether regulations on an individual's right to arms are an undue restriction on liberty and whether there is a correlation between guns and crime. Proponents of gun-control legislation assert that the strict enforcement of gun-control laws saves lives and reduces crime. By contrast, opponents of gun control assert that minimal restrictions on guns ensure that individuals have adequate means

for self-defense and that a wider distribution of firearms results in safer communities (britannica.com, 2020).

Table 4

Assessment of the Respondents on Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Monitoring

Indicators	Gun Operators/Owners		PNP Personnel	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Regulations on the acquisition, possession, and use of firearms by civilians.	3.76	0.54	3.86	0.40
Specific regulations on the acquisition, possession, and use of firearms by private security companies.	3.82	0.37	3.84	0.46
Regulations that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use.	3.87	0.33	3.92	0.27
Regional or international commitment(s) related to the regulation of civilian acquisition, possession or use of firearms undertaken by the Philippine government.	3.80	0.46	3.83	0.52
The types and characteristics of firearms to which civilians can lawfully have access.	3.78	0.49	3.86	0.40
Limitations on the number of firearms which civilians may own.	3.81	0.42	3.94	0.31
Categorization of firearms according to risk factors and how they are legally classified.	3.86	0.34	3.88	0.32
The conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm).	3.80	0.44	3.90	0.30
The system used to keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians.	3.80	0.46	3.88	0.32

The conditions for the transfer of ownership of firearms between civilians.	3.81	0.42	3.90	0.41
The measures in placed to regulate private entities engaged in selling firearms to civilians in the domestic market.	3.86	0.34	3.88	0.32
The conditions required for private entities to fulfil to qualify for a license to sell firearms.	3.79	0.48	3.81	0.52
The measures in placed to minimize the risk of firearms being misused by civilians.	3.82	0.40	3.90	0.30
The simplicity of process flow of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearm Registration.	3.85	0.35	3.86	0.40
The firearms registration by cluster municipal, Cities and Province to bring the services near to the doorstep of the registered firearm holders who want to possess	3.85	0.40	3.90	0.36
Overall Mean and SD	3.82	0.42	3.87	0.37
Description	Highly Implemented		Highly Implemented	

Legend:

- 3.51-4.00 Highly Implemented and observed /Highly Prevailing problem
- 2.51-3.50 Implemented and Observed/ Prevailing problem
- 1.51-2.50 Less Implemented and observed/ Less Prevailing Problem
- 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented/ Not Prevailing problem

Table 4 shows the assessment of the Respondents on Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Monitoring with an overall mean of 3.82 and 3.87 for gun owners/operators and PNP Personnel, respectively, which are both interpreted as ‘Highly Implemented.’

In specific, the gun owner respondents and PNP personnel commonly thought that indicator: Regulations that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use was highly implemented with the highest mean value of 3.87 and 3.92. From the result, it implies that the government is effective enough on the control of the in and out of questionable guns in the country. Doing this control will provide more safety against gun violence in the future.

Seemingly, indicator: The conditions required for private entities to fulfill to qualify for a license to sell firearms got the lowest mean value of 3.79 and 3.81 respectively. It is just right that the conditions to sell firearms must strictly be monitored to ensure safety against gun violence.

Accordingly, most laws regarding civilian ownership of firearms in the Philippines concern registration and background checks. There is also focus on disarming various militant groups, such as the Islamic separatist groups in Mindanao and the communist rebel groups such as the New People's Army to include Private Armies. The Philippines has also enacted laws because of many incidents of armed political violence before, during and after elections (en.wikipedia.org,2018).

Statement of the Problem #3: Is there a significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office?

Table 5

Test Of Significant Difference On the Assessment Of The Respondents On The Implementation Gun Control Policies In Terms of Enforcement

ENFORCEMENT					
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	0.016469	0.016469	1.995432	0.179617	4.60011
Within Groups	0.11555	0.008254			

Table-5 exhibits the significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office. The computed p-value of 0.179617 accepted the null hypothesis of no significant difference. This means that the assessments of both groups of respondents are significantly the same for both measured variables-- enforcement and monitoring.

Statement of the Problem #4: What are the problems encountered by PNP personnel and Gun owners and Operators of LTOPF in Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office.

Table 6

Problems Encountered by Gun Owners/Operators in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Enforcement

<i>Indicators</i>	Gun Owner/Operator		Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	
The enforcement of gun laws, rules and regulations by registered firearms Gun Owners and operators for limited duration of license granted has short period of time as validity.	3.91	0.32	Highly Prevailing Problem
Application of carrying firearms outside residence and the issuance of said license is limited only in the PNP National Headquarters, Manila which is difficult and costly in terms of travel with only short period of one (1) year validity.	3.89	0.40	Highly Prevailing Problem
For the new license/s and with old age applicants, the computerized application of the same contributed to the delay. It is difficulty to have an online application on LTOPF and Firearms Registration and the processes of downloading the required documents.	3.91	0.32	Highly Prevailing Problem
Have numerous documents for processing of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearms Registration.	3.90	0.35	Highly Prevailing Problem

Difficulty in processing firearm/s on cases like unintentionally loose firearms caused by the natural calamity, transfer of residence, and intentionally taken by thieves.	3.90	0.37	Highly Prevailing Problem
Short period of time in issuing notice on license, registration, permit to Gun holders and operators. Repeated giving of notice even to those already applied for tagging.	3.91	0.32	Highly Prevailing Problem
Time consuming in doing payments from the processing up to the approval of license, permit of LTOPF and Firearm Registration.	3.92	0.26	Highly Prevailing Problem
The approval on the results of the Neuro Psychiatric, Drug Test examination and Gun safety will take long period of time.	3.90	0.37	Highly Prevailing Problem
PNP personnel assigned in the evaluation of documents don't know how to appreciate the contents, in terms of the remarks that appeared in the issued National Police clearance even the case has been settled and same caused the disapproval of the applications.	3.90	0.35	Highly Prevailing Problem
Due to short lifespan validity of the license, permit, it discourages the licensee to file application of renewal.	3.87	0.45	Highly Prevailing Problem
Overall Mean and SD	3.90	0.35	Highly Prevailing Problem

Legend:

- 3.51-4.00 Highly Implemented and observed /Highly Prevailing problem
- 2.51-3.50 Implemented and Observed/ Prevailing problem
- 1.51-2.50 Less Implemented and observed/ Less Prevailing Problem
- 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented/ Not Prevailing problem

Table 6 reveals the problems encountered by Gun Owners/Operators in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Enforcement with an overall mean of 3.90 and is interpreted as '*Highly Prevailing Problem.*'

In specific, the gun owner respondents thought that indicator: Time consuming in doing payments from the processing up to the approval of license, permit of LTOPF and Firearm Registration was the highly prevailing problem with the highest mean value of 3.92. From the result, it implies that it is inconvenient for the gun owners to transact payments. Perhaps, online mode of payments was not effectively observed.

On the other hand, the indicator: Due to short lifespan validity of the license, permit, it discourages the licensee to file application of renewal got the lowest mean value of 3.87 among the gun owner respondents. This may imply that the respondents were not so bothered by this concern.

Table 7

Problems Encountered by Gun Owners/Operators in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Monitoring

Indicators	Gun Owner/Operator		Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	
Some Gun owners and Operators cannot follow the regulations on the acquisition, possession, and use of firearms. The PNP regulating body shall endeavor to act by monitoring and re-educating the firearm owners and Operators in order to avoid untoward incidents.	3.74	0.48	Highly Prevailing Problem
Some Gun Owners and Operators will change their addresses without any permission or notice to the PNP Regional office which created hard	3.74	0.48	Highly Prevailing Problem

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time to locate their whereabouts and time comes the latter will also experience difficulties of renewing his/her firearms and committed violation of existing laws, policies, rule and regulations.			
Its PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station shall regulates indefatigably the restriction or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms especially intended for civilian use however there is still unaccounted firearms owned by unregistered firearms holders which occasionally used by unscrupulous criminals in committing crimes.	3.74	0.46	Highly Prevailing Problem
There are inadequate number personnel to do the tasks to address the unsolved number of Gun related incident/violation PNP regulating body should promptly assist the request for firearm verification results as necessary requirement on the filling of complaints/charges.	3.74	0.46	Highly Prevailing Problem
Despite on the monitoring efforts by the PNP regulating body to Gun Owners and Operators on Implementation Gun Control Policies imposed, the same commits violations and penalties on the lapse or overdue of the renewal of their firearms licenses and permits to operate.	3.74	0.48	Highly Prevailing Problem
Close monitoring on the limitations of the number of firearms which civilians may owned shall be jointly implemented by the PNP however some Gun Owners and Operators take the risk of possessing unregistered firearms.	3.74	0.46	Highly Prevailing Problem

Categorization of firearms according to risk factors was classified strictly and monitored however some Gun owners and Operators insets to carry firearms out-side residence even without license and permits.	3.75	0.44	Highly Prevailing Problem
The conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm shall be monitored however some Gun owners and Operators failed to immediately reports to the nearest Police Units/Station.	3.72	0.51	Highly Prevailing Problem
PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station shall keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians however some Gun owners and Operators insets that their personal copy of license and permit was unintentionally lost and the same things they forgot their individuals Firearms emailed account and password which causes delay in the processing.	3.74	0.46	Highly Prevailing Problem
Monitoring the transfer of ownership of firearms owned Gun owners and Operators to the prospect secondary owner they only settled within their levels which it needs to interventions of the PNP regulating body as to the implementation and Gun Control Policies so that the transferred of the same should aligned with the firearms rule and regulations.	3.73	0.50	Highly Prevailing Problem
Overall Mean and SD	3.74	0.47	Highly Prevailing Problem

Legend:

- 3.51-4.00 Highly Implemented and observed /Highly Prevailing problem
- 2.51-3.50 Implemented and Observed/ Prevailing problem
- 1.51-2.50 Less Implemented and observed/ Less Prevailing Problem
- 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented/ Not Prevailing problem

Table 7 reveals the problems encountered by Gun Owners/Operators in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Monitoring with an overall mean of 3.74 and is interpreted as *'Highly Prevailing Problem.'*

Seemingly, the gun owner respondents believed that indicator: Categorization of firearms according to risk factors was classified strictly and monitored however some Gun owners and Operators insets to carry firearms out-side residence even without license and permits was the highly prevailing problem with the highest mean value of 3.75. This implies that PNP must be efficient enough in the categorization of firearms. Innovation on the process must be adopted to address clear categorization of firearms subject for licensing.

Also, the indicator: The conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm shall be monitored however some Gun owners and Operators failed to immediately got the lowest mean value of 3.72 among the gun owner respondents. This strongly suggests that gun owners must report to the nearest Police Units/Station for cases on lost firearms.

Table 8

Problems Encountered by PNP Personnel in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Enforcement

Indicators	PNP Personnel		Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	
Some of the PNP assigned from Regional Office down to Police Units/Station has difficulty in enforcement mainly the Republic Act No. 10591 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations and R.A. No 5487 the Security Industry Law if and when the Gun owners and operator did not support and cooperate with implementations on Gun control policies.	3.82	0.48	Highly Prevaling Problem
Enforcement on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms owned by Gun owners and Operators will be a headache on the part of the PNP implementing body if the latter hesitate to follow and obey the implementations of Gun Control policies.	3.80	0.53	Highly Prevaling Problem
PNP personnel assigned as regulatory implementers of the Gun Control Policies by Regional Office cannot systematically implement the implementation of the same, if the personnel from lower Police Units/Station and vice versa failed to appreciate, understand and lack of knowledge on the existing rules and regulations and policies.	3.86	0.35	Highly Prevaling Problem
Generally, the PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station encounter challenges and hardship in the enforcement and implementations of Gun Control Policies because of wrong interpretation and disinformation of knowledge on Oplan Confiscation, 5.Captured, Surrendered, Deposited, Abandoned and Forfeited firearms and ammunition (CCSDF)	3.78	0.58	Highly Prevaling Problem

The processing of License to Own and Posses Firearm (LTOPF) for gun owner and operator to be authorized to acquire, own/possess or use and sale firearms needs religious efforts on the part of the PNP implementing body to assists, evaluate and process their applications for issuances of licenses and permits.	3.83	0.48	Highly Prevailing Problem
Generally, the PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station encounter challenges and hardship in the implementation of Accounting, Disposition, Firearms with Expired Registration (ADFER).	3.87	0.35	Highly Prevailing Problem
In locating the dispositions of loose firearms to include unregistered firearms, registered firearms with expired firearms registration which resulted for lacked collaborated and coordination efforts with PNP key players on the enforcement of Gun Control Policies may contribute poor performances.	3.85	0.35	Highly Prevailing Problem
The conduct of investigations relative to claimed of lost firearm/s by the Gun owner and Operators play a crucial role on the part of the PNP investigating body to determine whether or not the claimant telling the truth or not. If the witness and complaining witness will not cooperate the applications of Wanted lost and firearm/s tagged may not granted.	3.79	0.53	Highly Prevailing Problem
Overall Mean and SD	3.82	0.45	Highly Prevailing Problem

Legend:

- 3.51-4.00 Highly Implemented and observed /Highly Prevailing problem
- 2.51-3.50 Implemented and Observed/ Prevailing problem
- 1.51-2.50 Less Implemented and observed/ Less Prevailing Problem
- 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented/ Not Prevailing problem

Table 8 reveals the problems encountered by PNP Personnel in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional

Office in terms of Enforcement with an overall mean of 3.82 and is interpreted as *'Highly Prevailing Problem.'*

From the tabulation, the PNP Personnel respondents thought that indicator: Generally, the PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station encounter challenges and hardship in the implementation of Accounting, Disposition, Firearms with Expired Registration was the highly prevailing problem with the highest mean value of 3.87. This implies that PNP must be efficient enough in the implementation of Accounting, Disposition, and Firearms with Expired Registration. Regular inventory of guns with expired licenses must be supported with technology.

The conduct of investigations relative to claimed of lost firearm/s by the Gun owner and Operators play a crucial role on the part of the PNP investigating body to determine whether the claimant is telling the truth or not. If the witness and complaining witness will not cooperate the applications of Wanted lost and firearm/s tagged may not granted got the lowest mean value of 3.79 among the PNP respondents. This strongly suggests that PNP must be resourceful enough in the conduct of investigation for the claim of lost firearms.

Table 9

Problems Encountered by PNP Personnel in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Monitoring

Indicators	PNP Personnel		Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	
Some Gun owners and Operators cannot follow the regulations on the acquisition, possession, and use of firearms. The PNP regulating body shall endeavor to take action by monitoring and re-educating the firearm owners and Operators in order to avoid untoward incidents.	3.86	0.40	Highly Prevailing Problem
Some Gun Owners and Operators will change their addresses without any permission or notice to the PNP Regional office which created hard time to locate their where-about and time comes the latter will also experience difficulties of renewing his/her firearms and committed violation of existing laws, policies, rule, and regulations.	3.84	0.46	Highly Prevailing Problem
Its PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station shall regulates indefatigably the restriction or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms especially intended for civilian use however there is still unaccounted firearms owned by unregistered firearms holders which occasionally used by unscrupulous criminals in committing crimes.	3.92	0.27	Highly Prevailing Problem
There is inadequate number personnel to do the tasks to address the unsolved number of Gun related incident/violation PNP regulating body	3.82	0.52	Highly Prevailing Problem

should promptly assist the request for firearm verification results as necessary requirement on the filling of complaints/charges.			
Despite on the monitoring efforts by the PNP regulating body to Gun Owners and Operators on Implementation Gun Control Policies imposed, the same commits violations and penalties on the lapse or overdue of the renewal of their firearms licenses and permits to operate.	3.86	0.40	Highly Prevailing Problem
Close monitoring on the limitations of the number of firearms which civilians may owned shall be jointly implemented by the PNP however some Gun Owners and Operators take the risked of possessing unregistered firearms.	3.94	0.31	Highly Prevailing Problem
Categorization of firearms according to risk factors was classified strictly and monitored however some Gun owners and Operators insets to carry firearms out-side residence even without license and permits.	3.88	0.32	Highly Prevailing Problem
The conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm shall be monitored however some Gun owners and Operators failed to immediately reports to the nearest Police Units/Station.	3.90	0.30	Highly Prevailing Problem
PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station shall keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians however some Gun owners and Operators insets that their personal copy of license and permit was unintentionally lost and the same things they forgot their individuals Firearms emailed account and password which causes delay in the processing.	3.88	0.32	Highly Prevailing Problem

Monitoring the transfer of ownership of firearms owned Gun owners and Operators to the prospect secondary owner they only settled within their levels which it needs to interventions of the PNP regulating body as to the implementation and Gun Control Policies so that the transferred of the same should aligned with the firearms rule and regulations.	3.90	0.41	Highly Prevailing Problem
Overall Mean and SD	3.88	0.37	Highly Prevailing Problem

Legend:

- 3.51-4.00 Highly Implemented and observed /Highly Prevailing problem
- 2.51-3.50 Implemented and Observed/ Prevailing problem
- 1.51-2.50 Less Implemented and observed/ Less Prevailing Problem
- 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented/ Not Prevailing problem

Table 9 presents the problems encountered by PNP Personnel in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Monitoring with an overall mean of 3.88 and is interpreted as ‘*Highly Prevailing Problem.*’

From the tabulation, the PNP Personnel respondents thought that indicator: Close monitoring on the limitations of the number of firearms which civilians may owned shall be jointly implemented by the PNP however some Gun Owners and Operators take the risk of possessing unregistered firearms was the highly prevailing problem with the highest mean value of 3.94. This implies that PNP must be motivated enough to monitor civilian number of guns owned to prevent gun violence in the future.

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On the other hand, the indicator: There is inadequate number personnel to do the tasks to address the unsolved number of Gun related incident/violation PNP regulating body should promptly assist the request for firearm verification results as necessary requirement on the filling of complaints/charges got the lowest mean value of 3.82 among the PNP respondents. This strongly suggests inventory and staffing management in the licensing department to address multi -tasking.

DISCUSSION**SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND
RECOMMENDATIONS**

This chapter deals with the summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations concerning the results of the study.

Summary

This study determined the Implementation and problems encountered in the Gun Control Policies by the PNP Regional Office.

The study covered 200 respondents. The 1st group of respondents was composed of 150-gun owners/operators, while the 2nd group of respondents was composed of 50 Personnel of PNP Firearms Licensing Offices in CARAGA Region. This study was conducted during the School Year 2021 – 2022. Data gathering will commence in June 2022.

The locale of the study was conducted in the PNP Firearms Licensing Offices in CARAGA Region, a counterpart of Philippine National Police Firearms and Explosives Office. The Philippine National Police Firearms and Explosives Office is the responsible office for the License To Own and Possess Firearm (LTOPF), and Firearms Application and Renewal including the Juridical Entity

Application for Regular License, License to Manufacture in Firearm and its Major Parts Small Arm Spare Parts and Accessories, License to Manufacture in Ammunition and/or Ammunition Reloading Components, License to Manufacture in Ammunition in Minor Parts and Accessories, License to Manufacture in Minor Parts and Accessories, License to Manufacture in Airguns/Airsoft, License to Manufacture in Bullet Proof Vest/Vestment, and License to Manufacture in Sporting Riflescope.

As to the research design, the study was conducted using the descriptive correlational research design (Anestis, & Houtsma, 2018). Foster, et al., (2020) posit that descriptive research provides a snapshot of the current state, while correlational research design is used to discover relationships among variables. Bloomfield and Fisher (2019) used descriptive correlational research design to describe the variables and to determine whether two or more variables are related. McAuley (2019) utilized the same research design to examine whether there were relationships between servant-leader behavior and organizational trust 12 performing-arts non-profit boards.

In particular, the descriptive phase was used in determining the profile of the licensed gun owner/operator respondents, and the personnel of PNP Firearms Licensing Office respondents as to

educational attainment, profession/occupation, number of firearms in ownership, number of years as holders of LTOPF, and type of issued LTOPF as well as length of service in the PNP and number of years serving as licensing officer, respectively. Using Weighted Mean, the assessments of the PNP personnel and Operators/Gun Holders with LTOPF respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of enforcement and monitoring were also determined. Finally, to test the significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office, ANOVA was used.

Findings

Statement of the Problem # 1.1.

In terms of Educational Attainment, majority (f=85, 57.0 percent) of the surveyed respondents are college undergraduate followed by college graduate (f=32, 21.0 percent), High School graduate and below (f=29, 19.0 percent) and four (4) Postgraduate or 3.0 percent of the total sample.

In terms of Profession/Occupation, most (f=55, 37.0 percent) of the respondents are working privately, followed by forty-six (46) respondents who are working in public office or in the government or 31.0 percent of the total sample. In addition, there are self-employed respondents which comprises 28.0 percent of the total

sample or forty-two (42) in number, and finally a handful (f=7, 5.0 percent) of respondents who are working abroad or part of the Overseas Filipino Workers (OFW) workforce.

In terms of Profession/Occupation, most (f=55, 37.0 percent) of the respondents are working privately, followed by forty-six (46) respondents who are working in public office or in the government or 31.0 percent of the total sample. In addition, there are self-employed respondents which comprises 28.0 percent of the total sample or forty-two (42) in number, and finally a handful (f=7, 5.0 percent) of respondents who are working abroad or part of the Overseas Filipino Workers (OFW) workforce.

In terms of the number of years as holder of LTOPF, most (f=87, 58.0 percent) of the gun owner- respondents have been holders for less than 5 years. Further, there are thirty-nine respondents or 26.0 percent of the total sample who are holders for 6-10 years, followed by 11-15 years (f=19, 13.0 percent), and 15 years and above (f=5, 3.0 percent).

In terms of type of issued license to own and possess firearms, Type 1 has the greatest number of possessors (f=87, 58.0 percent), followed by Type 3 (f=24, 16.0 percent), Type 2 (f=22, 15.0 percent), Type 4 (f=14, 9.0 percent), and lastly the Type 5 (f=3, 2.0 percent).

Statement of the Problem # 1.2.

In terms of length of service, the majority (f=23, 46.0 percent) of the respondents have been in service for 6-10 years, followed by 5 years and below (f=16, 32.0 percent), 11-15 years (f=6, 12.0 percent), and 15 years and above (f=5, 10.0 percent). In terms of number of years as a Licensing Officer, most (f=23, 46.0 percent) of the respondents have been in the position for 6-10 years and there are sixteen (16) respondents or 32.0 percent based on total sample to have below 5 years of tenure. Further, there are few (f=6, 12.0 percent) who hold the position for 11-15 years and five (5) (10.0 percent) officers with 15 years and above tenure.

Statement of the Problem # 2:

Assessments of the respondents on Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Enforcement had an overall mean of 3.86 and 3.80 for gun owners/operators and PNP Personnel, respectively, which are both interpreted as 'Highly Implemented.'

Basically, the gun owner-respondents believed that indicator: Civilians are required to have a License to Own and Posses Firearm (LTOPF) for him/her to be authorized to acquire, own/possess or use a firearm was highly implemented with the highest mean value of 3.96 while the PNP personnel assessed that indicator: There are

limits on the number of firearms that civilians may possess was highly implemented with the mean value of 3.85. From the result, it is very appropriate that LTOPF must strictly be followed with limit or control on the number of firearms to prevent gun violence in the future.

However, indicator: Only small arms may be registered by licensed citizens or licensed juridical entities for ownership, possession, and concealed carry; and Firearm must be secured inside a vehicle, or a motorcycle compartment got the lowest mean value of 3.66 and 3.76 respectively. It is imperative that all types of guns be regulated, and the gun owners must be extra cautious in securing their guns in the vehicle.

Assessments of the Respondents on Gun Control policies implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Monitoring had an overall mean of 3.82 and 3.87 for gun owners/operators and PNP Personnel, respectively, which are both interpreted as 'Highly Implemented.'

In specific, the gun owner respondents and PNP personnel commonly thought that indicator: Regulations that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use was highly implemented with the

highest mean value of 3.87 and 3.92. From the result, it implies that the government is effective enough on the control of the in and out of questionable guns in the country. Doing this control will provide more safety against gun violence in the future.

Seemingly, indicator: The conditions required for private entities to fulfill to qualify for a license to sell firearms got the lowest mean value of 3.79 and 3.81 respectively. It is just right that the conditions to sell firearms must strictly be monitored to ensure safety against gun violence.

Statement of the Problem # 3

The significant difference in the assessments of the PNP personnel and Gun operator and holders of LTOPF and firearms respondents on the Gun Control policies implemented by the PNP Regional Office had computed p-value of 0.179617 accepted the null hypothesis of no significant difference.

Statement of the Problem # 4

The problems encountered by Gun Owners/Operators in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Enforcement with an overall mean of 3.90 and is interpreted as *'Highly Prevailing Problem.'*

In specific, the gun owner respondents thought that indicator: Time consuming in doing payments from the processing up to the approval of license, permit of LTOPF and Firearm Registration was the highly prevailing problem with the highest mean value of 3.92. From the result, it implies that it is inconvenient for the gun owners to transact payments. Perhaps, online mode of payments was not effectively observed. On the other hand, the indicator: Due to short lifespan validity of the license, permit, it discourages the licensee to file application of renewal got the lowest mean value of 3.87 among the gun owner respondents. This may imply that the respondents were not so bothered by this concern.

On the other hand, the indicator: Due to short lifespan validity of the license, permit, it discourages the licensee to file application of renewal got the lowest mean value of 3.87 among the gun owner respondents. This may imply that the respondents were not so bothered by this concern.

The problems encountered by Gun Owners/Operators in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Monitoring had an overall mean of 3.74 and is interpreted as '*Highly Prevailing Problem.*'

Seemingly, the gun owner respondents believed that indicator: Categorization of firearms according to risk factors was classified strictly and monitored however some Gun owners and Operators insets to carry firearms out-side residence even without license and permits was the highly prevailing problem with the highest mean value of 3.75. This implies that PNP must be efficient enough in the categorization of firearms. Innovation on the process must be adopted to address clear categorization of firearms subject for licensing.

Also, the indicator: The conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm shall be monitored however some Gun owners and Operators failed to immediately got the lowest mean value of 3.72 among the gun owner respondents. This strongly suggests that gun owners must report to the nearest Police Units/Station for cases on lost firearms.

The problems encountered by PNP Personnel in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Enforcement had an overall mean of 3.82 and is interpreted as *'Highly Prevailing Problem.'*

From the tabulation, the PNP Personnel respondents thought that indicator: Generally, the PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station encounter challenges and hardship in the implementation of Accounting, Disposition, Firearms with Expired Registration was the highly prevailing problem with the highest mean value of 3.87. This implies that PNP must be efficient enough in the implementation of Accounting, Disposition, and Firearms with Expired Registration. Regular inventory of guns with expired licenses must be supported with technology.

The conduct of investigations relative to claimed of lost firearm/s by the Gun owner and Operators play a crucial role on the part of the PNP investigating body to determine whether the claimant is telling the truth or not. If the witness and complaining witness will not cooperate the applications of Wanted lost and firearm/s tagged may not granted got the lowest mean value of 3.79 among the PNP respondents. This strongly suggests that PNP must be resourceful enough in the conduct of investigation for the claim of lost firearms.

The problems encountered by PNP Personnel in Gun Control Policies Implemented by PNP Regional Office in terms of Monitoring

had an overall mean of 3.88 and is interpreted as '*Highly Prevailing Problem.*'

From the tabulation, the PNP Personnel respondents thought that indicator: Close monitoring on the limitations of the number of firearms which civilians may owned shall be jointly implemented by the PNP however some Gun Owners and Operators take the risked of possessing unregistered firearms was the highly prevailing problem with the highest mean value of 3.94. This implies that PNP must be motivated enough to monitor civilian number of guns owned to prevent gun violence in the future.

On the other hand, the indicator: There is inadequate number personnel to do the tasks to address the unsolved number of Gun related incident/violation PNP regulating body should promptly assist the request for firearm verification results as necessary requirement on the filling of complaints/charges got the lowest mean value of 3.82 among the PNP respondents. This strongly suggests inventory and staffing management in the licensing department to address multi -tasking.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions can be crafted:

1. Based on the assessment of the respondents, it can be concluded that the Gun Control policies were fairly implemented by the government despite of the challenges like the problems encountered in its enforcement and monitoring;
2. The problems encountered in enforcement and monitoring were highly prevalent thus it needs serious actions by the PNP organization.
3. It can further be concluded that there is a correlation between the Gun control policies and its problems encountered.

Recommendations

In relation with the findings and conclusions of the research, the following are the recommendations:

1. The PNP must conduct a series of orientation and forum among the gun owners / operators to strengthen the implementation of the gun control policies.
2. The PNP must adopt technology in a form of online app design to hasten the documentation and tracing of expired gun licenses;

3. PNP may revisit the gun control policies to craft strategies that can enhance gun licensing operation.
4. The Government must create more information campaign to prevent gun violence in the future.
5. There must be strategic planning to do intoevisit and troubleshoot the pressing problems relative to the gun licensing.

3 YEAR ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

Rationale of the Proposed Enhancement Program

Police Regional Office particularly in Firearms Registration and License to Own and Possess Firearms licensing Unit as the National Support and regulatory body of the Philippines National Police were mandated to regulate and evaluate the processing in terms of regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by civilians; specific regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private security companies; regulations that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use; regional or international commitment(s) related to the regulation of civilian acquisition, possession or use of firearms undertaken by the Philippine government; the types and characteristics of firearms to which civilians can lawfully have access; limitations on the number

of firearms which civilians may own; categorization of firearms according to risk factors and how they are legally classified; the conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm; the system used to keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians; the conditions for the transfer of ownership of firearms between civilians; the measures in placed to regulate private entities engaged in selling firearms to civilians in the domestic market; the conditions required for private entities to fulfil in order to qualify for a license to sell firearms; the measures in placed to minimize the risk of firearms being misused by civilians; the simplicity of process flow of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearm Registration; and the firearms registration by cluster municipal, Cities and Province to bring the services near to the doorstep of the registered firearm holders and the would be who want to possess.

Objectives of the Program

The purpose of the programs is to satisfy and give pleasurable services to gun owners and operators in line with laws, rules and regulation on acquisition of firearms. Notwithstanding, the assigned PNP personnel of Police Regional Office that cater the processing on acquisition of firearms will undergo reorientation seminars, training, and schooling for adaptation of new strategy and policies

in the implementation of gun control policies. To support the effective and efficient implementations and or to lessens or at least minimize the problems encountered on the Gun control policies of PNP Regional Office based on the results of the study, plans for enhancement have been crafted as categorize into three-year period programs.

Note: NEW with KRA and KPI

YEAR-1 Enhancement Program						
PROGRAMS for PNP personnel	OBJECTIVES AND OUTCOME	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Key Results Area (KRA)	PERSON IN-CHARGE	TIMEFRAME	BUDGET
-Blended Reorientation Training and Seminars of PNP personnel assigned as IT processor and evaluators and Investigators, implementers in the regional level and for cascading to the PNP personnel assigned in Police Station/Units	To be able to recall the application and understanding of laws, rules and regulations . R.A. No. 10591 and its IRR and R.A No. 5487 Security and Private Detective Industries. Familiarization of the process flow on the processing of LTOPF	PNP licensing officers can process efficiently the application for gun licensing	More gun owners will get licenses	Firearms processor and evaluators. Attorney or legals of the PNP.	One (1) month and it will be divided into two (2) or (4) four weeks.	One hundred thousand pesos (Php100, 000.00) to cover the food and snacks, gasoline, and virtual conference subscription.

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	and Firearms registration . To take note the Services with Satisfaction guarantee. No to fixer acts.					
<p>- Training/Seminars on digital or computerized online applications.</p> <p>- Continuous to impart during Police Information Continuing Education (PICE) the religious performance of sworn duty with Police Units/Station which they encounter challenges and hardship in the implementation of Accounting, Disposition, Firearms with Expired Registration (ADFER) and CCSDAF;</p> <p>- Augmentation of PNP personnel to</p>	<p>To speed up the processing on the application and renewal of licenses, permits and to have a paperless.</p> <p>- For specialization and avoidance of lapses in the performance of duty to address poor performances,</p>	<p>Gun Licenses can easily be processed using online platform .</p> <p>More tracking of expired guns in the Region</p>	<p>More gun owners will get licenses.</p> <p>More accounted expired guns</p>	<p>IT and ID's personnel Good for 2 to 3 PNP personnel as one (1) Official IT and two (2) alternatives.</p>	<p>Two (2) weeks</p>	<p>One hundred fifty thousand (Php150, 000.00) to cater the plane trip tickets, Board and logging, foods etc.</p>

be assigned as implementers and key positions of Unit assignment. -Training and Seminars of the SOSIA and FES PNP Investigators -Limitation and or avoid multiplication of handling tasks assignment of personnel which occupying key and vital position.	misconduct and irregular activities. Augmentations of at least 5 to 10 PNP personnel assign at PNP Regional Office with LTOPF and Firearms Licensing Office.					
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YEAR-2 Enhancement Program

PROGRAMS	OBJECTIVES AND OUTCOME	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Key Results Area (KRA)	PERSON IN-CHARGE	TIMEFRAME	BUDGET
Activation of PNP Provincial Offices to cater the regulations on acquisition of firearms.	-To bring the applications and approval of licensing, issuances of permit near to the doorstep and favorable implementation and to strengthen the accounting, identification	Easy access for the gun owners to register their guns	More gun owners will get licenses	Dedicated PNP personnel assigned as the frontlines on implementing the gun control policies per Police Station/Units.	Two (2) to Three (3) years from now as Caraga Region under Police Regional Office 13 will be consider one the Economic Zone as progressive	Five hundred thousand (Php500,000.00) to caters Food and snacks, Mobility, billeting of lecturer

	<p>n of firearms as to the owners of the same.</p> <p>- Delineation of services and responsibilities of the processing of application and approval not only by regionalize however o it should be provincialize.</p>				Region in the country.	
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YEAR-3 Enhancement Program

PROGRAM S	OBJECTIV ES AND OUTCOM E	Key Perform ance Indicator (KPI)	Key Result s Area (KRA)	PERSO N IN-CHARG E	TIMEFR AME	BUDGET
Creation of One-Stop Shop which strategically and conveniently located/installe d either PNP Regional Office co-located of MOA with the prospective Malls and or Shopping centers.	This is in compliance with the fast-growing Economic Zone in the country, wherein Caraga Region as the center for trade and industry after 3 years from now. It is expected the increase of applications to Own	Easy access for the gun owners to register their guns	More gun owners will get licenses	Composed of one team-Evaluator, IT processor, Finance, Supply Officer, Instructors, Psychologist, and Chemist for Drug test examination.	2 to 3 years from now.	One (1) or two (2) million for area improvement/installe tion, IT supplies (computer sets, tables, and chairs for PNP personnel and stakeholders). -Mobility and the like.

	and possess firearms which is the easiest ways and means of protecting themselves against unscrupulous criminals.					
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OLD without KRA and KPI

YEAR-1 Enhancement Program				
PROGRAMS for PNP personnel	OBJECTIVES AND OUTCOME	PERSON IN-CHARGE	TIMEFRAME	BUDGET
-Blended Reorientation Training and Seminars of PNP personnel assigned as IT processor and evaluators and Investigator, implementers in the regional level and for cascading to the PNP personnel assigned in Police Station/Units.	To be able to recall the application and understanding of laws, rules and regulations. R.A. No. 10591 and its IRR and R.A No. 5487 Security and Private Detective Industries. Familiarization of the process flow on the processing of LTOPF and Firearms registration. To take note	Firearms processor and evaluators . Attorney or legals of the PNP.	One (1) month and it will be divided into two (2) or (4) four weeks.	One hundred thousand pesos (Php100,000.00) to cover the food and snacks, gasoline, and virtual conference subscription.

	of the Services with Satisfaction guarantee. No to fixer acts.			
<p>- Training/Seminars on digital or computerized online applications.</p> <p>- Continuous to impart during Police Information Continuing Education (PICE) the religious performance of sworn duty with Police Units/Station which they encounter challenges and hardship in the implementation of Accounting, Disposition, Firearms with Expired Registration (ADFER) and CCSDAF.</p> <p>-Augmentation of PNP personnel to be assigned as implementers and key positions of Unit assignment.</p> <p>-Training and Seminars of the SOSIA and FES PNP Investigators</p> <p>-Limitation and or avoid multiplication of</p>	<p>To speed up the processing of the application and renewal of licenses, permits and to have a paperless.</p> <p>- For specialization and avoidance of lapses in the performance of duty to address poor performances, misconduct, and irregular activities. Augmentations of at least 5 to10</p>	<p>IT and ID's personnel Good for 2 to 3 PNP personnel as one (1) Official IT and two (2) alternates</p>	<p>Two (2) weeks</p>	<p>One hundred fifty thousand (Php150,000.00) to cater the plane trip tickets, Board and logging, foods etc.</p>

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<p>handling tasks assignment of personnel which occupy key and vital position.</p>	<p>PNP personnel assign at PNP Regional Office with LTOPF and Firearms Licensing Office.</p>			
YEAR-2 Enhancement Program				
PROGRAMS	OBJECTIVES AND OUTCOME	PERSON IN-CHARGE	TIMEFRAME	BUDGET
<p>Activation of PNP Provincial Offices to cater the regulations on acquisition of firearms.</p>	<p>-To bring the applications and approval of licensing, issuances of permit near to the doorstep and favorable implementation and to strengthen the accounting, identification of firearms as to the owners of the same. - Delineation of services and responsibilities of the processing of application and approval not only by regionalize however o it should be</p>	<p>Dedicated PNP personnel assigned as the frontlines' on implementing the gun control policies per Police Station/Units.</p>	<p>Two (2) to Three (3) years from now as Caraga Region under Police Regional Office 13 will be consider one the Economic Zone as progressive Region in the country.</p>	<p>Five hundred thousand (Php500,000.00) to caters Food and snacks, Mobility, billeting of lecturer</p>

	provincialize			
YEAR-3 Enhancement Program				
PROGRAMS	OBJECTIVES AND OUTCOME	PERSON IN-CHARGE	TIMEFRAME	BUDGET
Creation of One-Stop Shop which strategically and conveniently located/installed either PNP Regional Office co-located of MOA with the prospective Malls and or Shopping centers.	This is in compliance with the fast-growing Economic Zone in the country, wherein Caraga Region as the center for trade and industry after 3 years from now. It is expected the increase of applications to Own and possess firearms which is the easiest ways and means of protecting themselves against unscrupulous criminals.	Composed of one team-Evaluator, IT processor, Finance, Supply Officer, Instructors, Psychologist, and Chemist for Drug test examination.	2 to 3 years from now.	One (1) or two (2) million for area improvement/installation, IT supplies (computer sets, tables and chairs for PNP personnel and stakeholders). -Mobility and the like.

References

Acheson, R., & Butler, M. (2019). WPS and Arms Trade Treaty. In The Oxford Handbook of Women, Peace, and Security.

Ahram, A. (2020). Proxy Warriors. Stanford University Press.

Alpers, Philip and Michael Picard. 2021. Philippines — Gun Facts, Figures and the Law. Sydney School of Public Health, The University of Sydney. GunPolicy.org, 8 October. Accessed 9 November 2021. at: <https://www.gunpolicy.org/firearms/region/philippines>

Amnesty International. GUN VIOLENCE – KEY FACTS. Retrieved November 15, 2021 from <https://www.amnesty.org/en/what-we-do/arms-control/gun-violence/>

Anestis, M. D., & Houtsma, C. (2018). The association between gun ownership and statewide overall suicide rates. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 48(2), 204-217.

Anestis, MD; Houtsma, C (13 March 2017). "The Association Between Gun Ownership and Statewide Overall Suicide Rates". *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*. 48 (2): 204–217. doi:10.1111/sltb.12346. PMID 28294383. S2CID 4756779.

Bitan, D. T., Grossman-Giron, A., Bloch, Y., Mayer, Y., Shiffman, N., & Mendlovic, S. (2020). Fear of COVID-19 scale: Psychometric characteristics, reliability and validity in the Israeli population. *Psychiatry Research*, 289, 113100.

Blocher, J., Buell, S. W., Charles, J. D., & Miller, D. A. (2020). Pointing Guns. *Tex. L. Rev.*, 99, 1173.

- Bloomfield, J., & Fisher, M. J. (2019). Quantitative research design. *Journal of the Australasian Rehabilitation Nurses Association*, 22(2), 27-30.
- Bromund, T. At the 2021 UN Programme of Action on Small Arms Meeting, the US Should Get Real.
- Bustillo, J. C. M., & Mateo, J. T. I. (2020). Automated Incident Reporting Management System Using Mobile Technology. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 11(1).
- Buttrick, N. (2020). Protective gun ownership as a coping mechanism. *Perspectives on psychological science*, 15(4), 835-855.
- Caraga News Courier, (April 4, 2017), PNP-Caraga brings services closer to gun license applicants. Retrieved January 15, 2022 from <https://caraganewscourier.com/pnp-caraga-brings-services-closer-to-gun-license-applicants/>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, (2018). Web-based Injury Statistics Query and Reporting System (WISQARS), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control. Retrieved November 15, 2021 from <https://www.cdc.gov/injury/wisqars/index.html>

Cole, Suzanne N. (November 19, 2016). Association of Firearm Instructors – Glossary of Firearm Terms. Association of Firearm Instructors. Retrieved November 15, 2021 from <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0188S1QXU/>.

Concepcion, Bruce. 2019 'Firearm Numbers and Management in the Philippines.' Personal Interview with GunPolicy.org

Cook, P. J. (2020). Thinking about gun violence. *Criminology & Public Policy*, 19(4), 1371-1393.

Cusumano, E., & Ruzza, S. (2020). From Hybrid to Commercial Vessel Protection: The Italian Case. In *Piracy and the Privatisation of Maritime Security* (pp. 143-169). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.

David, C. C., Monterola, S. L. C., Paguirigan Jr, A., Legara, E. F. T., Tarun, A. B., Batac, R. C., & Osorio, J. P. (2018). School hazard vulnerability and student learning. *International journal of educational research*, 92, 20-29.

De Castro, J. A. C., & Jimenez, A. V. J. T. (2013). Recent Amendments and Legislation Affecting the Revised Penal Code of the Philippines. *Ateneo LJ*, 58, 289.

Director of Research Mike Picard. Manila: GunPolicy.org. 20 February

Donnelly, J., & Whelan, D. J. (2020). International human rights. Routledge.

Doucette, M. L., Crifasi, C. K., & Frattaroli, S. (2019). Right-to-carry laws and firearm workplace homicides: A longitudinal analysis (1992–2017). *American journal of public health*, 109(12), 1747-1753.

Emerson, R. W. (2019). Cronbach's alpha explained. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness (Online)*, 113(3), 327.

Fernandez, E., & Lopez, A., (November 15, 2021), Massive drive vs. loose guns ordered in BARMM, Caraga. Philippines News Agency. Retrieved January 15, 2022 from <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1159773>

Foster, K., Roche, M., Giandinoto, J. A., & Furness, T. (2020). Workplace stressors, psychological well-being, resilience, and caring behaviours of mental health nurses: A descriptive correlational study. *International journal of mental health nursing*, 29(1), 56-68.

Fridel, E. E. (2021). Comparing the impact of household gun ownership and concealed carry legislation on the frequency of mass shootings and firearms homicide. *Justice quarterly*, 38(5), 892-915.

- Galavís, N. G. (2020). Rule of law crisis, militarization of citizen security, and effects on human rights in Venezuela. *European Review of Latin American and Caribbean Studies/Revista Europea de Estudios Latinoamericanos y del Caribe*, (109), 67-86.
- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2019). *IBM SPSS statistics 26 step by step: A simple guide and reference*. Routledge.
- Gong, Y., & Goksel, O. (2019). Weighted mean curvature. *Signal Processing*, 164, 329-339.
- Halbrook, S. P. (2020). To Bear Arms for Self-Defense: A Right of the People or a Privilege of the Few?. Available at SSRN 3589749.
- Hill, T. D., Dowd-Arrow, B., Burdette, A. M., & Warner, T. D. (2020). Gun Ownership and Life Satisfaction in the United States. *Social Science Quarterly*, 101(5), 2121-2136.
- Hurka, S., & Knill, C. (2020). Does regulation matter? A cross-national analysis of the impact of gun policies on homicide and suicide rates. *Regulation & Governance*, 14(4), 787-803.
- Kalnow, A., Lloyd, C., Casey, J., & Little, A. (2019). Google forms-a novel solution to blended learning. *Journal of Education and Teaching in Emergency Medicine*, 4(2).

Kantack, B. R., & Paschall, C. E. (2020). Does “politicizing” gun violence increase support for gun control? Experimental evidence from the Las Vegas shooting. *Social Science Quarterly*, 101(2), 893-908.

Karp, A. (June 2018). Estimating Global Civilian Held Firearms Numbers. smallarmssurvey.org. Retrieved on November 30, 2021 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20180620231909/http://www.smallarmssurvey.org/fileadmin/docs/T-Briefing-Papers/SAS-BP-Civilian-Firearms-Numbers.pdf>

Karp, Aaron. 2018 ‘Civilian Firearms Holdings, 2017.’ Estimating Global Civilian-Held Firearms Numbers. Geneva: Small Arms Survey, the Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies, Geneva.

Kelsay, J. D., Silver, I. A., & Barnes, J. C. (2020). The association between adolescent gun ownership and gun carrying and adulthood violence and victimization. *Violence and victims*.

Magharei, M., Jaafari, S., Mansouri, P., Safarpour, A., & Taghavi, S. A. (2019). Effects of self-management education on self-efficacy and quality of life in patients with ulcerative colitis:

- a randomized controlled clinical trial. *International journal of community based nursing and midwifery*, 7(1), 32.
- Maurer, J.D., (November 2018), *The Purposes of Arms Control*, *Texas National Security Review*, Vol 2, Iss 1
<http://dx.doi.org/10.26153/tsw/870>
- McAuley, C. (2019). Relationships matter—Ideas for transforming the nonprofit boardroom. *Performance Improvement*, 58 (4), 13-20.
- McFarland, J., Hussar, B., Zhang, J., Wang, X., Wang, K., Hein, S., ... & Barmer, A. (2019). *The Condition of Education 2019*. NCES 2019-144. National Center for Education Statistics.
- Monteiro, L. H. (2020). More guns, less crime? A dynamical systems approach. *Applied mathematics and computation*, 369, 124804.
- NATO, (15 February 2021), *Small arms and light weapons (SALW) and mine action (MA)*, Retrieved November 15, 2021 from https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_52142.htm
- Nave, E. (2019). The Importance of the Arms Trade Treaty for the Implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals. *Journal of Conflict and Security Law*, 24(2), 297-324.
- Nystuen, G., & Egeland, K. (2019). The potential of the Arms Trade Treaty to reduce violations of international

humanitarian law and human rights law. In *Research Handbook on International Law and Peace*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

Pascua, J. R. (2018). The criminal investigation procedure of piat police Station: The level of awareness and compliance. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 7(11), 169-192.

Patterson, S. D., & Brandner, C. R. (2018). The role of blood flow restriction training for applied practitioners: A questionnaire-based survey. *Journal of sports sciences*, 36(2), 123-130.

Philippines. 2013 'Definition of Terms [Regulations].' Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act No. 10591, otherwise known as 'Comprehensive Firearms and Ammunition Regulation Act'; Rule I (Section 3), pp. 2-12. Manila: Congress of the Republic of the Philippines. Retrieved November 15, 2021 from <https://www.gunpolicy.org/firearms/citation/quotes/11158>

Pierre, J.M.(2019). The psychology of guns: risk, fear, and motivated reasoning. *Palgrave Commun* 5, 159. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-019-0373-z>

Reynolds, J. P., Stautz, K., Pilling, M., van der Linden, S., & Marteau, T. M. (2020). Communicating the effectiveness and

- ineffectiveness of government policies and their impact on public support: a systematic review with meta-analysis. *Royal Society open science*, 7(1), 190522.
- Rosenberg, M. (2021). Considerations for developing an agenda for gun violence prevention research. *Annual review of public health*, 42, 23-41.
- Sanny, L., Arina, A., Maulidya, R., & Pertiwi, R. (2020). Purchase intention on Indonesia male's skin care by social media marketing effect towards brand image and brand trust. *Management Science Letters*, 10(10), 2139-2146.
- Scholtz, S. E. (2021). Sacrifice is a step beyond convenience: A review of convenience sampling in psychological research in Africa. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 47, 12.
- Siegel, R. B., & Blocher, J. (2020). Why regulate guns?. *The Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics*, 48(4_suppl), 11-16.
- Singh, S., Gupta, B., Sharma, D., & Mishra, P. C. (2019). A Study of stress, coping, social support, and mental health in police personnel of Uttar Pradesh. *Indian journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 2 (2), 73.
- Smith, J., & Spiegler, J. (2020). Explaining gun deaths: gun control, mental illness, and policymaking in the American states. *Policy studies journal*, 48(1), 235-256.

- Smith, R. (2020). International human rights law. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Solovyeva, A., & Hynek, N. (2021). The paradox of success: Evolutionary dynamics between human rights and small arms. *Journal of Human Rights*, 1-20.
- Speak, A., Escobedo, F. J., Russo, A., & Zerbe, S. (2018). Comparing convenience and probability sampling for urban ecology applications. *Journal of applied ecology*, 55(5), 2332-2342.
- Spitzer, R. J. (2020). Gun accessories and the Second Amendment: assault weapons, magazines, and silencers. *Law & Contemp. Probs.*, 83, 231.
- Spitzer, R. J. (2020). *The politics of gun control*. Routledge.
- Swanson, J. W., Barry, C. L., & Swartz, M. S. (2020). Gun violence prevention and mental health policy. In *The Palgrave Handbook of American Mental Health Policy* (pp. 509-541). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Tannenbaum, D. I. (2020). Does the disclosure of gun ownership affect crime? Evidence from New York. *Journal of Public Economics*, 181, 104075.
- United Nations General Assembly, (25 February 2013). "International Instrument to Enable States to Identify and

Trace, in a Timely and Reliable Manner, Illicit Small Arms and Light Weapon" (PDF). unodc.org. United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime.

United Nations Regional Centre for Peace and Disarmament (undated). Programme of Action The United Nations Programme of Action on Small Arms and Light Weapons. Retrieved November 15, 2021 from <https://unrcpd.org/conventional-weapons/poa/>

van Zuiden, M., Savas, M., Koch, S. B., Nawijn, L., Staufenbiel, S. M., Frijling, J. L., ... & Olf, M. (2019). Associations among hair cortisol concentrations, posttraumatic stress disorder status, and amygdala reactivity to negative affective stimuli in female police officers. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*, 32(2), 238-248.

Vecino-Ortiz, A. I., & Guzman-Tordecilla, D. N. (2020). Gun-carrying restrictions and gun-related mortality, Colombia: a difference-in-difference design with fixed effects. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 98(3),

Vorobev, P., Greenwood, D. M., Bell, J. H., Bialek, J. W., Taylor, P. C., & Turitsyn, K. (2019). Deadbands, droop, and inertia impact on power system frequency distribution. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, 34(4), 3098-3108.

- Wamser-Nanney, R. (2021). Understanding gun violence: Factors associated with beliefs regarding guns, gun policies, and gun violence. *Psychology of violence*, 11(4), 349.
- Webster, D. W., McCourt, A. D., Crifasi, C. K., Booty, M. D., & Stuart, E. A. (2020). Evidence concerning the regulation of firearms design, sale, and carrying on fatal mass shootings in the United States. *Criminology & Public Policy*, 19(1), 171-212.
- Weller, Jac; Guilmartin, John; Ezell, Edward (November 7, 2017). "Small arm". *Britannica*. Encyclopædia Britannica, inc. Retrieved November 15, 2021 from <https://www.britannica.com/>
- Westefeld, John S.; Gann, Lianne C.; Lustgarten, Samuel D.; Yeates, Kevin J. (2016). "Relationships between firearm availability and suicide: The role of psychology". *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*. 47 (4): 271–277. doi:10.1037/pro0000089.
- WHO. 2021 'Inter-country Comparison of Mortality for Selected Causes of Death.' WHO Mortality Data Base. Geneva: World Health Organisation. 9 November
- Wolfson, J. A., Azrael, D., & Miller, M. (2020). Gun ownership among US women. *Injury prevention*, 26(1), 49-54.

Yang, Q., Yan, Q., Cai, J., Tian, J., & Guan, X. (2020). Neural network-based error-tracking iterative learning control for tank gun control systems with arbitrary initial states. *IEEE Access*, 8, 72179-72187.

Zeoli, A. M., & Webster, D. W. (2019). Firearm policies that work. *Jama*, 321(10), 937-938.

Нагорний, Б. (2019). ILLICIT FIREARMS TRAFFICKING.

JULIUS BURIAS MELLIJOR
Researcher

Annexes

RIZA C TOROTORO

Police Major
Acting Station Commander
Butuan City Police Station 1

Dear Ma'am,

Greetings!

The undersigned student is presently conducting a study entitled, **“IMPLEMENTATION AND PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED ON GUN CONTROL POLICIES BY PNP REGIONAL OFFICE TOWARDS ITS ENHANCEMENT”** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the completion of the degree, Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice.

In this regard, the undersigned is humbly requesting your good office to allow to conducts survey using convenient sampling techniques which are form parts of the important in the completion of my study. Rest assured that all data gathered from you will be kept in the highest level of confidentiality.

Your positive response in this request will be valuable contribution for the success of the study and will be highly appreciated. Thank you very much for your cooperation. God bless!

Very truly yours,

JULIUS B MELLIJOR

Researcher

EUNICE G GONZALES

Police Major
Station Commander
Butuan City Police Station 4

For Gun Owners and Operator (Respondents)

Dear Ma'am,

Greetings!

The undersigned student is presently conducting a study entitled, **“IMPLEMENTATION AND PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED ON GUN CONTROL POLICIES BY PNP REGIONAL OFFICE TOWARDS ITS ENHANCEMENT”** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the completion of the degree, Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice.

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Very truly yours,

JULIUS B MELLIJOR
Researcher

Dear Respondent,

Greetings!

The undersigned student is presently conducting a study entitled, **“IMPLEMENTATION AND PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED ON GUN CONTROL POLICIES BY PNP REGIONAL OFFICE TOWARDS ITS ENHANCEMENT”** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the completion of the degree, Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice.

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Very truly yours,

JULIUS B MELLIJOR
Researcher

Types of respondents:

- Gun Owners and Operators**
- PNP Personnel assigned Firearms Licensing**

Part 1. Profile of the two groups of respondents: Please put a tick (/) mark on the space provided corresponding to your best choice.

A. For the Gun Owners

1. Educational attainment:

- High school graduate and below
- College undergraduate
- College graduate
- Post graduate

2. Profession/Occupation:

- Public employment
- Private employment
- Self-employed
- Overseas employment

3. Number of firearms in possession/ownership

- 1-2
- 3 -5
- 6 -10
- 11-15

4. Number of years as since licenses to own and possessed firearms:

- 5 Years and below
- 6-10 Years
- 11-15 Years
- Above 15 Years

5. Type of Issued License To Own and Possess Firearms:

- Type 1
- Type 2

[] Type 3

[] Type 4

[] Type 5

Part 2. Assessment of the respondents on the enforcement and monitoring on the Implementations of Gun Control Policies.

Please put a tick (/) mark on the space provided for corresponding to your best choice. Please use this scale: 4 Strongly Agree; 3 Agree; 2 Disagree; and 1 Strongly Disagree .

Variables/Indicators	4	3	2	1
Enforcement on Gun Control Policies				
The acquisition, possession and use of firearms by civilians is governed mainly by Republic Act No. 10591 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations;				
The acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private companies are governed by RA 10591 and RA 5487 entitled An Act to Regulate the Organization and Operation of Private Detective, Watchmen Or Security Guards Agencies;				
Only small arms may be registered by licensed citizens or licensed juridical entities for ownership, possession and concealed carry;				
There are limits on the number of firearms that civilians may possess.				
Civilians are required to have a License to Own and Posses Firearm (LTOPF) for him/her to be authorized to acquire, own/possess or use a firearm.				
Firearms must always be concealed;				
Firearm must be secured inside a vehicle or a motor cycle compartment;				
Firearm shall not be brought inside places of worship, public drinking and amusement places and all other commercial or public establishment;				
Monitoring of Gun Control Policies				
Regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by civilians;				
Specific regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms by private security companies;				
Regulations that restrict or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms intended for civilian use;				

Regional or international commitment(s) related to the regulation of civilian acquisition, possession or use of firearms undertaken by the Philippine government;				
The types and characteristics of firearms to which civilians can lawfully have access;				
Limitations on the number of firearms which civilians may own;				
Categorization of firearms according to risk factors and how they are legally classified;				
The conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm);				
The system used to keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians;				
The conditions for the transfer of ownership of firearms between civilians;				
The measures in placed to regulate private entities engaged in selling firearms to civilians in the domestic market;				
The conditions required for private entities to fulfil in order to qualify for a license to sell firearms;				
The measures in placed to minimize the risk of firearms being misused by civilians;				
The simplicity of process flow of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearm Registration; and				
The firearms registration by cluster municipal, Cities and Province to bring the services near to the doorstep of the registered firearm holders who want to possess.				

Part 3. Assessment of the respondents (Gun Owner and Operators) on the Problems Encountered on the Gun Control Policies Towards Its Enhancement. Please put a tick (/) mark on the space provided for corresponding to your best choice. Please use this scale: 4 Strongly Agree; 3 Agree; 2 Disagree; and 1 Strongly Disagree.

Variables/Indicators	4	3	2	1
Problems Encountered on Gun Control Policies “Enforcement”				
The enforcement of gun laws, rules and regulations by registered firearms Gun Owners				

and operators for limited duration of license granted has short period of time as validity;				
Application of carrying firearms out-side residence and the issuance of said license is limited only in the PNP National Headquarters, Manila which is difficult and costly in terms of travel with only short period of one (1) year validity ;				
For the new license/s and with old age applicants, the computerized application of the same contributed the delay. It is difficulty to have an online application on LTOPF and Firearms Registration and the processes of downloading the required documents;				
Have numerous documents for processing of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearms Registration				
Difficulty in processing firearm/s on cases like: unintentionally loose firearms caused by the natural calamity, transfer of residence, and intentionally taken by thieves;				
Short period of time in issuing notice on license, registration, permit to Gun holders and operators. Repeated giving of notice even to those already applied for tagging.				
Time consuming in doing payments from the processing up to the approval of license, permit of LTOPF and Firearm Registration.				
The approval on the results of the Neuro Psychiatric, Drug Test examination and Gun safety will take long period of time;				
PNP personnel assigned in the evaluation of documents don't know how to appreciate the contents, in terms of the remarks that appeared in the issued National Police clearance even the case has been settled and same caused the disapproval of the applications				
Due to short lifespan validity of the license, permit, it discourages the licensee to file application of renewal.				
Problems Encountered on Gun Control Policies "Monitoring"				

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<p>The PNP assigned to regulate failed to monitor the expiration of firearms license and permit in order to avoid penalty and charges for non-renewal or updating the same;</p>				
<p>Lack of available information, knowledge of some members of the PNP assigned to monitors the status firearms owned by the Gun owners and Operators in term of data/s appeared on their records from the actual description of the firearm/s;</p>				
<p>Some PNP regulating body committed wrong entry of records as to the names of the owner, description and detailed of firearms;</p>				
<p>Cannot able to immediately identify whether or not such individual possess license firearms, when he or she involved in crime using any kind or type of firearms;</p>				
<p>The PNP Regional Office cannot account as to the numbers of firearm/s Gun owners, and operators;</p>				
<p>Unable to locate the address and whereabouts of firearms held by Gun owners and operators as to the exact location, address and the secondary address;</p>				
<p>Some of the PNP assigned to regulate and monitor cannot immediately categorized the firearms according to risk factors and how they are legally classified;</p>				
<p>The conditions for possession of firearms by Gun Holders and Operators (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of Holders firearm were not properly checked and monitored by the PNP Regional Office;</p>				
<p>Some of the PNP assigned to monitor and implement the notice for inspection and actual accounting of firearms are unable to inform ahead of time; and</p>				

<p>The PNP Regional Office cannot immediately monitor or committed delay in the identifications of whether or not the firearm/s involved in criminal complaint and or case pending its judgment in court either registered and unregistered.</p>				
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-And-

Part 1. Profile of the two groups of respondents: Please put a tick (/) mark on the space provided corresponding to your best choice.

For the PNP personnel

1. Educational Attainment

- Baccalaureate Degree
- Masters Degree
- PhD Degree
- Others: _____

2. Length of Service in the PNP

- 5 Years and below
- 6-10 Years
- 11-15 Years
- Above 15 Years

3. Number of years a Licensing Officer

- 5 Years and below
- 6-10 Years
- 11-15 Years
- Above 15 Years

Part 3. Assessment of the respondents (PNP Personnel) on the Problems Encountered on the Gun Control Policies Towards Its Enhancement. Please put a tick (/) mark on the space provided for corresponding to your best choice. Please use this scale: 4 Strongly Agree; 3 Agree; 2 Disagree; and 1 Strongly Disagree.

Variables/Indicators	4	3	2	1
Problems Encountered on Gun Control Policies “Enforcement”				
Some of the PNP assigned from Regional Office down to Police Units/Station has difficulty in enforcement mainly the Republic Act No. 10591 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations and R.A. No 5487 the Security Industry Law if and when the Gun owners and operator did not support and cooperate with implementations on Gun control policies;				
Enforcement on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms owned by Gun owners and Operators will be a headache on the part of the PNP implementing body if the latter hesitate to follow and obey the implementations of Gun Control policies;				
PNP personnel assigned as regulatory implementers of the Gun Control Policies by Regional Office cannot systematically implement the implementation of the same, if the personnel from lower Police Units/Station and vice versa failed to appreciate, understand and lack of knowledge on the existing rules and regulations and policies;				
Generally, the PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station encounter challenges and hardship in the enforcement and implementations of Gun Control Policies because of wrong interpretation and disinformation of knowledge on Oplan Confiscation, Captured, Surrendered, Deposited, Abandoned and Forfeited firearms and ammunition (CCSDAF),				
The processing of License to Own and Posses Firearm (LTOPF) for gun owner and operator to be authorized to acquire, own/possess or use and sale firearms needs religious efforts on the part of the PNP implementing body to assists, evaluate and process their applications for issuances of licenses and permits;				
Generally, the PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station encounter challenges and hardship in the implementation of Accounting, Disposition, Firearms with Expired Registration (ADFER);				
In locating the dispositions of loose firearms to include unregistered firearms, registered firearms with expired firearms registration which resulted for lacked collaborated and coordination efforts with				

<p>PNP key players on the enforcement of Gun Control Policies may contribute poor performances; and</p>				
<p>The conduct of investigations relative to claimed of lost firearm/s by the Gun owner and Operators play a crucial role on the part of the PNP investigating body to determine whether or not the claimant telling the truth or not. If the witness and complaining witness will not cooperate the applications of Wanted lost and firearm/s tagged may not granted.</p>				
<p>Problems Encountered on Gun Control Policies “Monitoring”</p>				
<p>Some Gun owners and Operators cannot follow the regulations on the acquisition, possession and use of firearms. The PNP regulating body shall endeavor to take action by monitoring and re-educating the firearm owners and Operators in order to avoid untoward incidents;</p>				
<p>Some Gun Owners and Operators will change their addresses without any permission or notice to the PNP Regional office which created hard time to locate their where-abouts and time comes the latter will also experience difficulties of renewing his/her firearms and committed violation of existing laws, policies, rule and regulations;</p>				
<p>Its PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station shall regulates indefatigably the restriction or prohibit the import and export of firearms or certain types of firearms especially intended for civilian use however there is still unaccounted firearms owned by unregistered firearms holders which occasionally used by unscrupulous criminals in committing crimes;</p>				
<p>There is an inadequate number personnel to do the tasks to address the unsolved number of Gun related incidents/violation. PNP regulating body should promptly assist the request for firearm verification results as necessary requirement on the filling of complaints/charges</p>				
<p>Despite on the monitoring efforts by the PNP regulating body to Gun Owners and Operators on Implementation Gun Control Policies imposed, the same commits violations and penalties on the lapse or overdue of the renewal of their firearms licenses and permits to operate;</p>				

Close monitoring on the limitations of the number of firearms which civilians may owned shall be jointly implemented by the PNP however some Gun Owners and Operators take the risked of possessing unregistered firearms;				
Categorization of firearms according to risk factors was classified strictly and monitored however some Gun owners and Operators insets to carry firearms out-side residence even without license and permits;				
The conditions for possession of firearms by civilians (e.g. safe storage requirements, reporting of theft or loss of firearm shall be monitored however some Gun owners and Operators failed to immediately reports to the nearest Police Units/Station;				
PNP Regional Office down to Police Units/Station shall keep a records of firearms acquired or owned by civilians advise to keep their record however some Gun owners and Operators insets that their personal copy of license and permit was unintentionally lost and the same things they forgot their individuals Firearms emailed account and password which causes delay in the processing;				
Monitoring the transfer of ownership of firearms owned by Gun owners and Operators to the prospect secondary owner they only settled within their levels which it needs the interventions of the PNP regulating body as to the implementation and Gun Control Policies so that the transferred of the same should aligned with the firearms rule and regulations;				

Part 2. Assessment of the respondents on the enforcement and monitoring on the Implementations of Gun Control Policies. Please put a tick (/) mark on the space provided for corresponding to your best choice. Please use this scale: 4 Strongly Agree; 3 Agree; 2 Disagree; and 1 Strongly Disagree .

Variables/Indicators	4	3	2	1
Enforcement on Gun Control Policies				
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5487 entitled An Act to Regulate the Organization and Operation of Private Detective, Watchmen Or Security Guards Agencies;				
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Limitations on the number of firearms which civilians may own;				
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The system used to keep a record of firearms acquired or owned by civilians;				
The conditions for the transfer of ownership of firearms between civilians;				

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The conditions required for private entities to fulfil in order to qualify for a license to sell firearms;				
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The simplicity of process flow of License to Own and Possess Firearm and Firearm Registration; and				
The firearms registration by cluster municipal, Cities and Province to bring the services near to the doorstep of the registered firearm holders who want to possess.				

JULIUS B MELLIJOR
 Researcher

CURRICULUM VITAE

JULIUS BURIAS MELLIJOR, RC
Police Senior Master Sergeant
 Blk 3 Lot 53 Northtown Subdivision
 Brgy. Libertad, Butuan City
 Email Add: gentmells3721@yahoo.com
 Contact Number: Smart- 09190943874

Qualification:

Current Police Senior Master Sergeant,
 Badge Number: 174222, Philippine National Police
 Graduate of MS in Criminology SY 2020 Cagayan de Oro College, Pinma Edu.
 Graduate of BS in CRIMINOLOGY SY 2004, License Criminologist 2013
 Graduate of Public Junior Leadership Course
 Registered Regular Member of Professional Criminologist Association of the Phil, Inc.
 Class 2013-02 Criminal Investigation Course
 Completed Training of Air-to-Ground Operations Seminar (AGOS)
 Class 2008-Alpha, CQB-CLOSE QUARTER BATTLE COURSE
 Class 2008-Alpha, PNP Special Counter Operation Unit Training
 Class 2007-11 Peace and Development Outreach Program Training
 First Aid and Responders Course
 Completed Firework Safety Seminar
 Member of Balangahai Pistol and Riffle Practical Shooters Asso. INC.
 Member of Phil. Shooters Match Officers Confederation (PSMOC)
 Member of The Fraternal Order of Eagle Phil. Eagles (TFOEPE)

PERSONAL DATA

Age: 39
 Date of Birth: July 7, 1982
 Gender: Male
 Civil Status: Married
 Height: 5'7"
 Weight: 67 kg
 Nationality: Filipino

WORK EXPERIENCE

1. Position: **Police Senior Master Sergeant (PSMS)**

Duration: October. 1, 2019-present

Company: Government

Job Description:

Designated as Firearm and License to Own and Possess Firearm processor/records and supply PNCO of Regional Civil Security Unit 13 Caraga with mother unit Civil Security Group. In-charge parallel investigation for endorsement of revocation of licenses, attained court proceeding as witness of firearm involved incident and entertain client/s. Inspect Security Agencies, Gun Store and conduct actual and surprise Post-to-Post inspection within the area of responsibility. Previously, assigned in maneuvering companies as rifleman and undergone major combat operation in the hinterland of Mindanao and performed various police functions in different city and municipal police stations. Perform search and rescue, retrieval operation during calamities and typhoons. Impart knowledge and skills to the comrades and to the community and performed public awareness such as information drive, house to house visitation and school visitation and conducted lectures.

2. Position: **Part-time Faculty**

Duration: March 2014-present

Company: Holy Child of Butuan College

Job Description;

Teach different investigation and intelligence subjects to the students and Fundamental Marksmanship and actual Short pistol and rifle combat firing. Instill safety and security awareness and share field experiences and lesson learned.

3. Position: **Factory Worker**

Duration: Feb. 2004-Feb. 2005

Company: Wu-Kong PTE.LTD and HTI PTE. LTD

Job Description:

Heavy and light plant machine operator, fabricator, layout planning of metallic and furniture. MIG ELCT welders and acetylene operator.

4. Position: **Merchandiser, Bundlers and Advertisers**

Duration: 2003-2004

Company: ACE PROMOTION INC.

Job Description:

Nestle products merchandiser responsible in-charge of receiving stocks, orders, and shelves maintenance of goods in selling area and

bodega. Observe FIFO-First-In and First-Out and maintain cleanliness and orderliness.

5. Position: Sale-Staff

Duration: 2002-2003

Company: GOLDEN ABC INC. and BLUES BROTHERS COMPANY

Job Description:

Welcome and entertain customers in the selling area, promote dry goods, met weekly and monthly quotas, conduct inventory and give full customers satisfaction.

6. Position: Utility/Helper

Duration: 1997-1999

Company: GOVERNMENT

Job Description:

On-the-Job workers of the city slaughter house assist in paper works and maintain the safety and security of the workers of the plant.

7. Position: SA-Student Assistance

Duration: Feb.1999- March 2003

Company: Saint Joseph Institute of Technology

Job Description:

Security In-charge of the College Library, check students entrance card, borrowers card and maintain the area for conducive to learning and studies. Purchaser assistance of the entire school, canvass, purchase, review and receive orders, check the quantity and quality of the products.

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Post Education	-Graduate of MS in Criminology @COC, Phinma-2019-2020	
Tertiary Level	- Graduate of BS in Criminology @SJIT	- 2003-2004
Secondary Level	- Agusan National High School	- 1998-1999
Primary Level	- Buenavista East Central Elementary School	- 1994-1995

TRAININGS/SEMINARS

Date	Topic/Course Title
Jan. 7, 2016	-Handgun and 2.Gun Competition Rules

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Pres.	Gov. Datu Sunarto T. Mangungudat o/PSMOC
Oct. 15-30, 2015	-Patrol Officers Basic Course (POBC) PRO 13
June 14, 2015-Aug 21, 2015	-Basic Course in Practical Shooting and Gun Safety Seminar/BPRPSAI
Oct. 24, 2014	-Fireworks Safety Seminar/ Firearms Explosives Office, Camp Crame, Quezon City.
Sept. 8-19, 2014	-Police First Responders Course/Police Reg'l Training Services.
May 4, 2012	-e-BLOTTER SYSTEM USERS TRAINING /Directorate for Investigation and Detective Management, PCSUPT ALEX PAUL I MONTEAGUDO, CESE
May 16 - June 17, 2011	- Peace and Dev't Outreach Program Training / Hqs 10 th Infantry (AGILA) Division, Phil. Army
Dec. 17, 2010-Jan 11, 2011	- City and Municipal Police Station Unit Training/ (RSTU) Hqs PRO 11, Catitipan Davao City.
Sept 16-Nov 07, 2008	- CLOSE QUARTER BATTLE COURSE- CQB 2008-A/ 11 th Regional Mobile Group, PRO 11 Firing Range, Camp Catitipan, Davao City
July 10, 2008	- One Day Purpose Driven Life Seminar/ Rev Liberato T. Diao
May 13-15, 2008	-Demolition Techniques and Explosive Ordnance Reconnaissance Agent/RSTU, PRO 11
Feb 18-June 18, 2008	- PNP Special Counter Operation Unit Training/RSTU, PRO 11
Mar 15-16, 2007	-Family Link Philippines/Personnel Of FLP, Manila
Feb 02, 2007-Feb 02, 2008	-Public Safety Basic Recruit Course/ PPSC. RTS XI
Dec 01, 2006-Feb 18, 2007	-Police Recruit Orientation Course/RSTU, Camp Catitipan, Davao City
Feb 2004-Sept 2005	- Safety and Security Preparedness Seminar and Firefight Seminar/Wu-Kong and HTI PTE LTD, EPZA, Rosario Cavite, Manila, Philippines
May 16-18, 2003	- Close THAT SALE TECHNIQUES

AWARD RECEIVED

1. **20-Medalya ng Papuri/Excellent Awards** - Philippine National Police. **PRO 11 &13**
2. **30-Certificates of Commendation** - Philippine National Police, **PRO 11 & 13**
3. Recipients of Private and Gov't Scholar - Non-Government & Government Full Scholars
4. 1st Runner-Up 21K Graduation Run -Phil. Public Safety College, RTS11 (2008)
 1st Runner-Up 7K Graduation Run -Phil. Public Safety College, RTS13 (2017)
 1st Runner-Up 7K Graduation Run -Phil. Public Safety College, RTS11 (2021)

ELIGIBILITIES

Board Passer RA6506 (CRIM)	-CAGAYAN DE ORO CITY
SPO EXAM (NAPOLCOM)	-DAVAO CITY
PO EXAM (NAPOLCOM)	-DAVAO CITY
PNP ENTRANCE EXAM	-BUTUAN CITY, CARAGA

REFERENCES

Engr. Zoerix C. Colima
 Private Companies Builders of Celebes
 Cel, # 09065314237

Mr. Joey V. Valeroso
 JVV Farm, Proprietor/Businessman
 Cel, # 09985705090

This is to certify that above information are true and correct to the best of my ability and knowledge.

PSMS JULIUS B MELLIJOR, MSCrim, RCrim
 Student/Researcher

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GRADUATE SCHOOL